

6G-SANDBOX

Supporting Architectural and technological
Network evolutions through an intelligent, secured
and twinning enabled Open eXperimentation
facility

Funded by
the European Union

Deliverable D5.3

INTERMEDIATE REPORT ON KPI AND KVI VALIDATION

Date: 31/08/2024

Version: 1.0

Grant Agreement	101096328
Document number	D5.3
Document title	Intermediate Report on KPI and KVI Validation
Lead Beneficiary	KEYD
Editor(s)	Filip Ivanovic (KEYD)
Author(s)	Michael Dieudonné (KEYB), Pedro Merino, Pablo Herrera, María del Mar Moreno, Javier Jiménez, Francisco Luque (UMA), Filip Ivanovic, Torsten Iversen, Abhishek Bakshi (KEYD), (FOG), Nikolaos Gkatzios, Georgios Theodoropoulos (INF), (OWO), (TID), Harilaos Koumaras, George Makropoulos, Vasilis Pitsilis (NCSR), Fofy Setaki, Elina Theodoropoulou, George Lyberopoulos (COS), (NOKIA), Antti Pauanne (OULU), (ICTF), (ON), (EURE), Bjoern Riemer (FOKUS), (LNV).
Dissemination level	Public
Contractual date of delivery	31 August 2024
Status	Final
Version	1.0
File name	6G-SANDBOX_D5.3_V1.0.pdf

Document History

Version

V1.0	First version
V1.1	Incorporation of performance measurements
V1.2	Ready for peer review
V2.0	Final Version

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Abstract	8
Keywords	8
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Document Structure	9
1.2 Target Audience	9
2 Testing and Measurement Approach	10
2.1 KPIs in Target for Interim Measurements	11
2.2 The Reference Trial Network Benchmark Concept	12
2.3 Basic System-Software Performance Measurement Methodology	13
2.3.1 Measuring & Testing Tool	13
2.3.2 Related Metrics	14
2.3.3 Test Scope & Test Cases.....	15
2.4 End-to-End Performance Measurement Methodology	18
2.4.1 Measuring & Testing Tool	18
2.4.2 Related Metrics	19
2.4.3 Test Scope & Test Cases.....	19
3 Athens Measurement Topologies and Results	21
3.1 System/Software level Measurements	21
3.1.1 Reference Trial Network	21
3.1.2 Enterprise (ATHONET) Trial Network.....	24
3.1.3 Open5gs/MOCN – Distributed Agents deployment Trial Network.....	26
3.2 End-2-End Measurements	28
3.2.1 Enterprise (ATHONET) Trial Network.....	28
3.3 Assurance Testing	30
3.4 Result Analysis	30
4 Berlin Measurement Topologies and Results	32
4.1 System/Software Level Measurements	32
4.1.1 Reference Trial Network	32
4.1.2 ESXi Open5gCore Trial Network.....	35
4.1.3 ONE Open5gCore Trial Network	37
4.2 End-to-End Measurements	39
4.2.1 Open5Gcore Trial Network	39
4.3 Assurance Testing	41
4.4 Result Analysis	42

5	<i>Malaga Measurement Topologies and Results</i>	43
5.1	System/Software level Measurements	43
5.1.1	Reference Trial Network.....	43
5.1.2	UPF P4 Trial Network.....	46
5.1.3	POLARIS Trial Network.....	48
5.2	End-2-End Measurements	50
5.2.1	Open5GS Trial Network.....	50
5.3	Assurance Testing	52
5.4	Result Analysis	52
6	<i>Oulu Measurement Topologies and Results</i>	54
6.1	System/Software level Measurements	54
6.1.1	Reference Trial Network.....	54
6.2	End-2-End Measurements	57
6.2.1	End-to-End network.....	57
6.3	Assurance Testing	58
6.4	Result Analysis	59
7	<i>Result Analysis and Comparison</i>	60
7.1	Inter Platform Results	60
7.1.1	Aggregated Results per KPI.....	61
7.2	Intra Platform Results	64
7.2.1	Athens.....	65
7.2.2	Berlin.....	65
7.2.3	Malaga.....	65
8	<i>Conclusions</i>	66
9	<i>References</i>	67
	<i>Annex 1 – TCP Throughput Log Extraction and Analysis</i>	68
	<i>ANNEX 2 – Athens Detailed Results</i>	69
	Reference Trial Network.....	69
	Enterprise (ATHONET) Trial Network.....	69
	Open5gs/MOCN – Distributed Agents deployment Trial Network.....	70
	<i>ANNEX 3 – Berlin Detailed Results</i>	72
	Reference Trial Network.....	72
	ESX Open5gCore Trial Network.....	72
	ONE Open5gCore Trial Network.....	73
	<i>ANNEX 4 – Malaga Detailed Results</i>	75

Reference Trial Network.....	75
UPF P4 TRIAL NETWORK.....	75
POLARIS Trial Network	76
<i>ANNEX 5 – Oulu Detailed Results</i>	<i>77</i>
Reference Trial Network.....	77

List of FIGURES

Figure 1: LoadCore Tool Deployment Architecture	14
Figure 2: LoadCore interconnection schematic	15
Figure 3: IxChariot Web- GUI Representation of the Test Topology	19
Figure 4: Measurement Topology and setup for the Reference Trial Network in Athens platform.....	22
Figure 5: Downlink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-Reference TN	23
Figure 6: Uplink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-Reference TN	23
Figure 7: Downlink DD Distribution for Athens platform-Reference TN.....	23
Figure 8: Uplink DD Distribution for Athens platform-Reference TN	23
Figure 9: Availability Results for Athens Platform – Reference TN.....	24
Figure 10: Measurement Topology and setup for the Enterprise (ATHONET) Trial Network in Athens platform (all in OTE site).....	24
Figure 11: Downlink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-ATHONET TN.....	25
Figure 12: Uplink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-ATHONET TN.....	25
Figure 13: Downlink DD Distribution for Athens platform-ATHONET TN	26
Figure 14: Uplink DD Distribution for Athens platform-ATHONET TN	26
Figure 15: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Open5GS/MOCN Trial Network in Athens platform	26
Figure 16: Downlink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-Open5GS/MOCN TN	27
Figure 17: Uplink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-Open5GS/MOCN TN	27
Figure 18: Downlink DD Distribution for Athens platform-Open5GS/MOCN TN.....	28
Figure 19: Uplink DD Distribution for Athens platform-Open5GS/MOCN TN	28
Figure 20: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Enterprise (ATHONET) Trial Network in Athens platform...28	
Figure 21: Min/Max/Avg Throughput for Athens platform – end-to-end	29
Figure 22: Athens End-to-End ICMP Measurements	30
Figure 23: Athens End-to-End Speed Test Measurements	30
Figure 24: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Reference Trial Network in Berlin platform.....	33
Figure 25: Downlink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform-Reference TN	34
Figure 26: Uplink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform-Reference TN.....	34
Figure 27: Downlink DD Distribution for Berlin platform-Reference TN	34
Figure 28: Uplink DD Distribution for Berlin platform-Reference TN	34
Figure 29: Availability Results for Berlin Platform – Reference TN.....	35
Figure 30: Measurement Topology & Setup for the ESXi Open5gCore Trial Network in Berlin platform	35
Figure 31: Downlink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform-ESXi Open5GCore TN	36
Figure 32: Uplink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform- ESXi Open5GCore TN.....	36
Figure 33: Downlink DD Distribution for Berlin platform- ESXi Open5GCore TN	37
Figure 34: Uplink DD Distribution for Berlin platform- ESXi Open5GCore TN	37
Figure 35: Measurement Topology & Setup for the ONE Open5gCore Trial Network in Berlin platform	38
Figure 36: Downlink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform-ONE Open5GCore TN.....	39
Figure 37: Uplink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform- ONE Open5GCore TN	39
Figure 38: Downlink DD Distribution for Berlin platform- ONE Open5GCore TN	39
Figure 39: Uplink DD Distribution for Berlin platform- ONE Open5GCore TN.....	39
Figure 40: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Open5Gcore e2e Trial Network in Berlin platform	40
Figure 41:End-to-End Throughput Measurements for Berlin Platform	41
Figure 42: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Reference Trial Network in Malaga platform	43
Figure 43: Downlink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform-Reference TN.....	45
Figure 44: Uplink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform-Reference TN	45
Figure 45: Downlink DD Distribution for Malaga platform-Reference TN	45
Figure 46: Uplink DD Distribution for Malaga platform-Reference TN.....	45
Figure 47: Availability Results for Malaga Platform – Reference TN	46

Figure 48: Measurement Topology & Setup for the UPF P4 Trial Network in Malaga platform	47
Figure 49: Downlink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform-UPF P4 TN.....	48
Figure 50: Uplink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform-UPF P4 TN	48
Figure 51: Downlink DD Distribution for Malaga platform-UPF P4 TN	48
Figure 52: Uplink DD Distribution for Malaga platform-UPF P4 TN.....	48
Figure 53: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Polaris Trial Network in Malaga platform.....	49
Figure 54: Downlink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform-Polaris TN	50
Figure 55: Uplink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform- Polaris TN	50
Figure 56: Downlink DD Distribution for Malaga platform- Polaris TN.....	50
Figure 57: Uplink DD Distribution for Malaga platform- Polaris TN	50
Figure 58: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Open5GS Trial Network in Malaga platform.....	51
Figure 59: End-to-End Throughput Measurements for Malaga Platform.....	52
Figure 60: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Reference Trial Network in Oulu platform	54
Figure 61: Downlink UPL Distribution for Oulu platform-Reference TN.....	55
Figure 62: Uplink UPL Distribution for Oulu platform-Reference TN.....	55
Figure 63: Downlink DD Distribution for Oulu platform-Reference TN	56
Figure 64: Uplink DD Distribution for Oulu platform-Reference TN	56
Figure 65: Availability Measurements for Oulu Platform – Reference TN.....	56
Figure 66: OULU measurement topology for End-To-End tests	57
Figure 67: End to End throughput measurements for the Oulu Platform	58

List of TABLES

Table 1: System/Software Level Measurements for KPI Validation: Metrics, Measurements & Test Cases.....	14
Table 2: End-to-End Measurements for KPI Validation: Collected Metrics, Measurements & Test Cases.....	19
Table 3:PDR Results for Athens Platform -Reference TN.....	22
Table 4: UEDR, PLR Results for Athens Platform -Reference TN.....	22
Table 5: UPL, DD Results for Athens Platform -Reference TN	22
Table 6: CPL Results for Athens Platform -Reference TN.....	23
Table 7: PDR Results for Athens Platform -ATHONET TN	25
Table 8: UEDR, PLR Results for Athens Platform -ATHONET TN	25
Table 9: UPL, DD Results for Athens Platform -ATHONET TN	25
Table 10: CPL Results for Athens Platform -ATHONET TN	26
Table 11: PDR Results for Athens Platform - Open5GS/MOCN TN	27
Table 12:EUDR, PLR Results for Athens Platform - Open5GS/MOCN TN.....	27
Table 13: UPL, DD Results for Athens Platform - Open5GS/MOCN TN.....	27
Table 14: CPL Results for Athens Platform - Open5GS/MOCN TN.....	28
Table 15: Athens Platform Radio Configuration for End-to-End Measurements	29
Table 16:PDR, UEDR End-to-End Results for Athens Platform.....	29
Table 17: MOS End-to-End Results for Athens Platform	30
Table 18: Assurance Testing Results for Athens Platform	30
Table 19: PDR Results for Berlin Platform -Reference TN.....	33
Table 20: : UEDR, PLR Results for Berlin Platform -Reference TN	33
Table 21: UPL, DD Results for Berlin Platform -Reference TN	33
Table 22: CPL Results for Berlin Platform -Reference TN	34
Table 23: PDR Results for Berlin Platform -ESXi Open5gCore TN	36
Table 24: UEDR, PLR Results for Berlin Platform -ESXi Open5gCore TN	36
Table 25: UPL, DD Results for Berlin Platform -ESXi Open5gCore TN.....	36
Table 26: CPL Results for Berlin Platform -ESXi Open5gCore TN	37

Table 27: PDR Results for Berlin Platform -ONE Open5gCore TN.....	38
Table 28: UEDR, PLR Results for Berlin Platform -ONE Open5gCore TN.....	38
Table 29: UPL, DD Results for Berlin Platform -ONE Open5gCore TN	38
Table 30: CPL Results for Berlin Platform -ONE Open5gCore TN.....	39
Table 31: Berlin Platform Radio Configuration for End-to-End Measurements	40
Table 32: PDR, UEDR End-to-End Results for Berlin Platform.....	41
Table 33: DD End-to-End Results for Berlin Platform	41
Table 34: MOS End-to-End Results for Berlin Platform	41
Table 35: Assurance Testing Results for Berlin Platform	41
Table 36: PDR Results for Malaga Platform -Reference TN	44
Table 37: UEDR, PLR Results for Malaga Platform -Reference TN	44
Table 38: UPL, DD Results for Malaga Platform -Reference TN.....	44
Table 39: CPL Results for Malaga Platform -Reference TN	45
Table 40: UPL, DD Results for Malaga Platform - UPF P4 TN.....	47
Table 41: CPL Results for Malaga Platform - UPF P4 TN	48
Table 42: PDR Results for Malaga Platform -Polaris TN.....	49
Table 43: Results for Malaga Platform -Polaris TN	49
Table 44: UPL, DD Results for Malaga Platform -Polaris TN	49
Table 45: CPL Results for Malaga Platform -Polaris TN.....	50
Table 46: Malaga Platform Radio Configuration for End-to-End Measurements	51
Table 47: PDR, UEDR End-to-End Results for Malaga Platform	51
Table 48: DD End-to-End Results for Malaga Platform	52
Table 49: MOS End-to-End Results for Malaga Platform.....	52
Table 50: Assurance Testing Results for Malaga Platform.....	52
Table 51: PDR Results for Oulu Platform -Reference TN	55
Table 52:UEDR, PLR Results for Oulu Platform -Reference TN	55
Table 53: UPL, DD Results for Oulu Platform -Reference TN.....	55
Table 54: CPL Results for Oulu Platform -Reference TN	56
Table 55: Oulu Platform Radio Configuration for End-to-End Measurements	57
Table 56: PDR, UEDR DD End-to-End Results for Oulu Platform.....	58
Table 57: DD End-to-End Results for Oulu Platform	58
Table 58: MOS End-to-End Results for Oulu Platform	58
Table 59: Assurance Testing Results for Oulu Platform.....	58
Table 60: 5G Core System Specifications per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)	60
Table 61: Peak Data Rate Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)	61
Table 62: Average User Experienced Data Rate Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN).....	61
Table 63: Delta Measurements of Average User Experienced Data Rate Measurements from the base platform (Malaga).....	62
Table 64: Packet Loss Rate Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN).....	62
Table 65: Delta Measurements of Packet Loss Rate Measurements from the base platform (Athens).....	62
Table 66: Average User Plane Latency Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)	63
Table 67: Delta Measurements of Packet Loss Rate Measurements from the base platform (Oulu)	63
Table 68: Average Delay Deviation Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)	63
Table 69: Delta Measurements of Delay Deviation Measurements from the base platform (Oulu).....	64
Table 70:: Average Control Plane Latency Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)	64
Table 71: Delta Measurements of Control Plane Latency Measurements from the base platform (Berlin)	64

ABSTRACT

This report covers the steps taken to implement testing solutions in the 6G-SANDBOX project as of August 31st 2024. An initial test scope is defined, as well as a main set of KPIs that will be put under test. Two main types of tests are conducted: those testing network cores, or end to end tests that test a full network setup, RAN included. Two Keysight tools are employed for this task, LoadCore for the former and IxChariot for the latter. All 4 6G-SANDBOX platforms (Athens, Berlin, Malaga, Oulu) were put under test, with multiple different trial networks defined and tested at each platform. This report introduces the concept of the Reference Trial Network, which was used during this process to achieve calibration between the platforms. The overall concepts of Inter-Platform and Intra-Platform calibration are also defined, both of which leverage the concept of the Reference Trial Network to provide 6G-SANDBOX users the ability to contextualize any and every measured result. Measurement results from multiple different test cases are presented. Each platform presents an analysis of these results, what they mean for the platforms performance and potential explanations for any outliers. The performance of each Reference Trial Network implementation is also compared in greater detail. The testing process detailed within was successful, in terms of result production and the drawing of large- and small-scale conclusions. A noticeable delta in the performance of the Reference Trial Network between the 4 platforms has led to the realization that future iterations of the Reference Trial Network need to be defined more granularly, especially in terms of the hardware and virtualization specifications. The difficulties encountered in the implementation of the testing solutions mean that the future process of automating the testing process will need to be approached more carefully and critically than previously expected. This report is an important stepstone for 6G-SANDBOX and will greatly inform and guide the path of continuing testing work in the project.

KEYWORDS

Performance KPIs, Trial Network, Experimentation, Testing methodology, Mobile Networks, 6G SANDBOX Platforms

1 INTRODUCTION

The document builds upon the next generation network KPIs analysis of D2.1 [1], that is based on the background set by the Standards Development Organizations (SDOs) (e.g., ITU-R and 3GPP) and the relevant 6G SANDBOX platform technologies. It extends the work presented in D5.1 [2] by describing the practical applicability of the testing & measurement solutions (systems and software) defined. This work will be circumvented by D5.5 that will provide the conclusive outcome on KPIs and KVI validation of the project.

The overarching testing and experimentation processes and toolchain have been specified in D5.1 [2], and their appropriate system-wise implementation is the foundation to ensure the reliable collection and validation of KPIs and KVIs, ensuring the customer-in-focus principles of the project. The project has selected a phased approach in which in the first phase, effort has been put to the installation of the identified state-of-the-art (SOTA) metering systems and appropriate and common configuration of the same testing scripts and parameterization so that to ensure transparency and repeatability of the executed results. Expecting a mature outcome of the project's automation developments, the measurements reported herein are manual and target to validate the metering and testing principles using a mutually agreed first set of KPIs, agreed by all platforms to reflect the common level of their technological readiness.

The measurements are also performed with an incremental approach, starting with baseline system/software measurements, and concluding with the end-to-end, user perception values.

1.1 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

The core part of the document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 covers the background of the testing and measurement approach undertaken during the period covered by this report. The key ideas underpinning the testing methodology are introduced, as well as the main set of KPIs to be measured and the overall technical scope of the devices under test. Each test case is described in detail, from the goals of its implementation to the technical details behind its implementation. Methods used to postprocess and present any generated data are also described. This section is divided into two main subsections, covering both the basic system-software level testing and the End-to-End level testing.
- Sections 3, 4, 5, 6 are dedicated to each of the 6G-Sandbox platforms, those being Athens, Berlin, Malaga and Oulu respectively. Each of these platforms has the capability to support various (in terms of Core Network, RAN, basic infrastructure and deployment alternatives) Trial Networks. As such, these sections start by presenting the different topologies each platform has established for measurement. Afterwards, text execution results in the form of the relevant KPIs are presented for each topology.
- Section 7 provides an overall result analysis and comparison of all results obtained across the platforms. This is divided into two main subsections, the first of which being a direct comparison between each platforms deployment of the so called "Reference" configuration. The second subsection covers the basic analysis of all other configurations deployed by each platform, comparing them to the reference configuration to identify performance differences. The section also provides an outlook of KPIs and KVIs and measurements to be performed in the coming period which will be reported in following deliverables.
- Section 8 concludes on the results presented in this report and process of obtaining these.

1.2 TARGET AUDIENCE

The release of the deliverable is public, intending to expose the overall 6G-SANDBOX facility to a wide variety of research individuals and communities. From specific to broader, different target audiences for D2.1 [1] are identified as detailed below:

- The Project Consortium to validate the KPIs and KVI's evaluated, and the test specifications and methodologies to evaluate these. This is to ensure unity in the procedure of obtaining the results and benchmarking platforms within the consortium, thereby making sure that KPIs and KVI's are evaluated using a common approach.
- The Research Community and funding EC Organization to i) summarize the 6G-SANDBOX scope, objectives and intended project innovations, ii) detail the 6G-SANDBOX Facility and the four platforms as well as the targeted KPIs and KVI's that shall be measured provided technological advancements.
- The vertical actors that will be engaged to the project with the process of the open calls and will utilize the 6G-SANDBOX facility to conduct their experiments.
- The public in general for obtaining a better understanding of the scope and capabilities of the 6GSANDBOX project.

2 TESTING AND MEASUREMENT APPROACH

6G-SANDBOX is being designed as a testing infrastructure with the customer in mind. This is evident in all its facets, including the design of the testing methodology and specifications. As the development of these methodologies advances and implementation begins, it is important to consider the perspective of the 6G SANDBOX and how they will use the system. The data generated by 6G-SANDBOX must be useful to them, not just in its novelty, but in their ability to use 6G-SANDBOX to interpret the actual contextual importance of the data. The delta of the results from previous iterations of a given component or trial network, the comparison of that delta to previously recorded ones, and the extrapolation of these results into farther reaching conclusions are all necessary capabilities of the 6G-SANDBOX system if it is to be an effective tool for the 6G SANDBOX end users. These end users can be divided into two broad categories: Experimenters, and future 6G-SANDBOX platform operators.

For an Experimenter, the main goal of their interaction with 6G-SANDBOX is to receive data about the performance of the component(s) they wish to put under test. There are two key issues here. Firstly, the inherent flexibility and variety in configuration present within the 6G-SANDBOX system means that just providing the raw data to experimenter is useless, as they do not have a full understanding of the capabilities of the platform/trial network that their test is being run on. This is further compounded by the second issue, that being that the relative novelty of 6G as a technology means that the amount of extant data of networks running in a 6G context to compare potential results against is extremely limited. To resolve both issues, the testing methodologies of 6G-SANDBOX are being designed such that they can provide the experimenter with baseline measurements of the trial network they are using so that the performance of the network when integrated with their component under test can be compared to this baseline and performance deltas can be presented. This puts the experimenters' results into context and gives them an actual understanding of what effect the inclusion of their component has had on the network. This process of dynamically measuring the baseline performance of a given trial network for the purposes of contextualizing end user results will henceforth be referred to as the **Calibration** of a 6G-SANDBOX Trial Network.

In terms of the bigger picture, this method of calibration has two main dimensions in which it can be leveraged. A trial network with known components, parameters and calibrated results can be replicated on a different platform, after which the calibrated results of the two platforms can be compared by the experimenter to make decisions about which platform best suits their testing needs. This process will henceforth be referred to as **Inter-Platform Calibration**. On the other hand, when operating within one platform, the experimenter may have the need to evolve or change the capabilities of the trial network over time. Calibration measurements can be made each time the trial network changes to ensure the experimenter understands what the expected results are at every stage. This process will henceforth be referred to as **Intra-Platform Calibration**.

Both calibration methods are also useful and necessary for the second user group of 6G-SANDBOX, those being the future platform operators. Inter-Platform Calibration will allow these operators to compare their platform as they develop it to the existing 6G-SANDBOX platforms, allowing them to ensure some level of baseline performance parity with the existing platforms. During the development of their own platform, Intra-Platform Calibration will be used for them to understand how the inclusion of each of their network components impacts the performance and capabilities of their platform.

The development of these two calibration methods are the main driving factors behind the work described in this deliverable. The following sections will detail implementation of the first testing methodologies, and how those methodologies are used in both inter and intra-platform calibration efforts.

Moreover, one of the main tenets of 6G-SANDBOX is its focus on the automation of the testing process. By leveraging the ELCM, 6G Library, Keysight Campaign Manager and OpenTAP, 6G-SANDBOX experimenters are expected to run tests without having to manually engage and configure tools. As these key components are still under development, in parallel the focus must be put on the lower-level and the accurate metering, which is a cornerstone towards providing correct and reliable results. Setting this as the target of this interim reporting, the tests in this report have been conducted manually. This means a tester directly interfacing with the user interface (UI) of a testing tool, inputting network parameters and test specifications, and monitoring the test during runtime. The processing of the data is also done manually, either through the analysis of the results in each tool UI or examining the readable log (.csv) files and processing the trace (.pcap) files with dedicated applications. This will be detailed per case in the subsections that follow.

2.1 KPIs IN TARGET FOR INTERIM MEASUREMENTS

Extensive analysis of the KPIs in target of 6G SANDBOX has already been performed in Deliverable 2.1 [1] together with relevant target values as well as assignment for evaluation to 6G SANDBOX platforms. All these KPIs are planned to be measured within the scope of 6G-SANDBOX by the project's completion, but for the purposes of this interim testing implementation phase, the most indicative and common subset of these KPIs is chosen. This is done by consortium consensus based on which KPIs are the most interesting or useful for the development/benchmarking of the testing platforms.

The selected set of KPIs, from the full list described in [1] that are in scope of the interim tests are as follows:

- Peak Data Rate (PDR)
- User Experienced Data Rate (UEDR)
- Packet Loss Rate (PLR)
- User Plane Latency (UPL)
- Control Plane Latency (CPL)
- Delay Deviation (DD)
- Availability (AVL)

The acronyms listed for these KPIs are used throughout the rest of this report. These KPIs are spread across three of the families described in Deliverable 2.1, those being Capacity, Latency and Availability.

As mentioned previously, this deliverable is a record of efforts undertaken to implement and validate the initial set of testing methodologies within 6G-SANDBOX as a subtle basis for the final expanded scope. Currently the goals include the development and the calibration of the measurement systems, producing the first real tests and exploring the maturity of each of the 6G SANDBOX platforms. As such, implementation begins at a very basal level. All platforms support one or multiple 5G network cores and have installed the appropriate testing and measuring systems, based on the selected tools capabilities. Specifically, for the relevant metrics collection, the project has followed an incremental approach, where measurements are first collected considering the **basic**

system/software level, and **end-to-end** including the radio interface impact. This distinction, important to identify the areas of superiority and/or improvement across platforms, mandates the establishment of different measurement configurations (i.e., as application, probes, scripts etc.) and related test cases and scripts, and as such is detailed separately in the subsequent paragraphs.

For the end-to-end measurements, one additional KPI was added due to its relevance in such tests:

- MOS Score (MOS)

MOS (Mean Opinion Score) is a numerical measure of the human-judged overall quality of the VoIP call quality. It is a value that ranges from 0 at the worst and 5 at the best. There is also an additional version of this KPI called the R value, which ranges from 0 to 120, offering higher granularity than the basic MOS score. This KPI is a new entry, not initially reported in D2.1, but judged as an interesting and available measure for end-to-end performance result reporting.

For each of the KPIs listed, the appropriate testing tool is selected, followed by the formulation of the subsequent test scope definitions and specifications. Five test cases have been defined to be executed in each measurement topology, where Test Cases 1-4 are done on the baseline system/software core configurations and implemented in LoadCore, while test case 5 is implemented on the End-to-End configurations with IxChariot. The following paragraphs describe the process in more detail.

2.2 THE REFERENCE TRIAL NETWORK BENCHMARK CONCEPT

All the platforms within 6G-SANDBOX support multiple different and unique trial networks, each able to be configured in a variety of different ways. This poses a question towards the uniform verification and validation of each of the platforms: how can the baseline parity between each of the current and potential future 6G-SANDBOX platforms be confirmed? Furthermore, how can future trial networks on any given platform be calibrated if there is no understanding of some baseline performance to measure deltas from. These are the key driving factors behind the decision to introduce the concept of a **Reference Trial Network** to 6G-SANDBOX.

The Reference Trial Network is a trial network within 6G-SANDBOX whose key parameters and components are defined universally and platform-agnostically. These are things like the network core, the number of subscribers, the hardware assignments to any given virtualized deployments, etc. Furthermore, hardware allocations to any virtualized environment/software are also kept consistent to provide peak performance parity. Such a trial network should ideally be able to run on any 6G-SANDBOX platform with performance that is in relative parity to all other platforms. The scope of this concept can be scaled up and down depending on the which aspects of the platforms are going to be tested. For example, a Reference Trial Network is defined for both baseline System/Software-level and End-to-End configurations. The Trial Network is systemically described as part of WP3 and WP4 activities, following the template initially defined and enhanced in the project, that can be found in the project's github repository¹.

The usage of these Trial Networks allows for the interrogation of underlying deltas between each platform. Standardizing as much of a trial network as possible allows for issues in base hardware or network infrastructure at a given platform to be identified as they would be the only remaining source for performance disparities between platforms. In this way, the Reference Trial Network is used to aid in Inter-Platform Calibration. The Reference Trial Network is also used for Intra-Platform Calibration. By gaining an understanding of the performance of the Reference Trial Network at baseline scope such as the system/software level configuration, once the simulated RAN is replaced with a real RAN in the End-to-End configuration any performance deltas with the new version can be attributed to the addition of the RAN and investigated further. This ability to gradually

¹ https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/TNLCM/tree/main/tn_template_lib

increase the scope and calibrate along the way leads to a more in depth understanding of the capabilities, performance, and limitations of individual components within each platform.

As well as this, the Reference Trial Network concept can serve a practical purpose as 6G-SANDBOX expands and more platforms are/wish to be added into the ecosystem. The 6G Library can be used to install all the necessary components and infrastructure, but the Reference Trial Network can be used as a yardstick: any prospective 6G-SANDBOX platform must be able to run a Reference Trial Network or multiple and show test results within some expected range. In this way, the consistency of 6G-SANDBOX as a testing ecosystem can be ensured as it grows.

For the core testing version of the Reference Trial Network, Open5GS was chosen as the core due to its open-source nature and the fact that its simple deployment meant that it could be easily deployed at all platforms. The Open5GS deployments would be allocated 4GB of RAM and 4 CPU cores, with the choice of exact deployment method (docker, virtual machine, etc.), left up to the individual platform's discretion. The rest of the Open5GS parameters would be left in their default installation states. The LoadCore middleware would also be installed in the network, with hardware allocations left up to the individual platforms as it would not affect performance. The two agents shown in Section 2.1, those being the ones emulating a RAN and a DN, would be allocated 4 CPU cores each, and 8GB of RAM to facilitate the large amounts of traffic they would be generating. All their other parameters would be set to their default values as well.

For the scope of this document the Reference Trial Network has been used for baselining the basic system/software measurements. For the end-to-end measurements, each platform has selected the incorporation of its most appropriate equipment focusing to generate the highest performance results.

2.3 BASIC SYSTEM-SOFTWARE PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT METHODOLOGY

The project has put significant effort in measuring from the perspective of the infrastructure (system and core network (CN) level) understanding that due to the softwarisation and virtualization of the mobile network functions where the plethora of computational resources and options for configuration incur a complexity, meticulous system-level measurements are important and can deterministically lead to the identification of areas for improvements through the appropriate system expansions and reconfigurations. It is important to stress that the basic system/software measurements in target consider the appropriate simulation of the mobile traffic, which is practically imposed by the radio layer such on-air downlink/uplink bitrates) so that to be realistic and complement appropriately end-to-end measurements. This has driven the selection of the tool that can appropriately simulate UE and RAN traffic patterns and is reflected and noted in the test cases/scripts developed and relevant parameters configuration.

The System-software performance measurements have been conducted to all prevailing 5G+ network deployment options supported by each platform, using the same test cases configuration, to ensure that the generated results will be of the same kind. Respective analytical results are provided and can be considered an interesting performance benchmarking for intra-platform evaluations.

2.3.1 MEASURING & TESTING TOOL

As described in Deliverable 5.1, LoadCore is a tool which can allow for the emulation and testing of elements of the network core, as depicted in Figure 1. The Middleware component is the seat of the central intelligence of the LoadCore Platform. The Test Users login to the MDW and configure/execute tests, view/download results. The actual Core components are emulated using LoadCore agents, which can also simulate traffic to test the capabilities of other core components which are under test. This makes it uniquely suitable to perform in depth measurements on the platform cores.

Figure 1: LoadCore Tool Deployment Architecture

It must be noted that for Downlink measurements the LoadCore DN Agent is the transmitter, and the UE/RAN Agent is the receiver, whereas for the Uplink the opposite holds. In both cases, and due to the LoadCore MW setup, for each measurement topology the respective 5G Core Network is intervened, similarly to traffic originating from a real UE. With such setup it is possible to simulate the traffic behavior of more than one UEs, a capability that has been appropriately utilized where necessary.

2.3.2 RELATED METRICS

The LoadCore tool is used to collect metrics for the validation of all KPIs following the measurement principles extensively analyzed in Deliverable 2.1 [1]. Table 1 below is summarizing the metrics and related statistical measurements that are used in the results presented in this report used to validate the target KPIs through the execution of the respective test cases further detailed in Section 2.3.3.

Table 1: System/Software Level Measurements for KPI Validation: Metrics, Measurements & Test Cases

KPI	Metrics Collected	Measurements	Relevant Test Case
Peak Data Rate (PDR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TCP/HTTP Downlink Data Rate (Mbps) TCP/HTTP Uplink Data Rate (Mbps) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Peak/Max value 95th Percentile² value 	Test Case #1.1 – Single UE
User Experienced Data Rate (UEDR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TCP/HTTP Downlink Data Rate (Mbps) TCP/HTTP Uplink Data Rate (Mbps) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5th Percentile value Peak/Max value 	Test Case #1.2 – Multiple UEs
Packet Loss Rate (PLR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TCP Packets Sent (number) TCP Packets Received (number) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage of Packets (Sent-Received)/Sent 	Test Case #1.2 – Multiple UEs
User Plane Latency (UPL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UDP Downlink Packet Time Delay (ms) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Average value of all samples 	Test Case #2 – Multiple UEs

² the value where 95% of all measurements are under it, and 5% of measurements are over it

KPI	Metrics Collected	Measurements	Relevant Test Case
Control Plane Latency (CPL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UDP Uplink Packet Time Delay (ms) 	2. Number of samples per delay range	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Idle to Transmission ready Time (ms) 	1. Average value of all samples	Test Case #3 – Multiple UEs
Delay Deviation (DD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UDP Downlink Packet Deviation (ms) 	1. Average value of all samples	Test Case #2 – Multiple UEs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UDP Uplink Packet Deviation (ms) 	2. Number of samples per deviation range	
Availability (AVL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core Uptime without failure 	1. Core config (specified) performance till failure occurrence (hrs)	Test Case #4 – Multiple UEs

2.3.3 TEST SCOPE & TEST CASES

The use of LoadCore to test the 5G Next-Gen Core (NGC) (SA Stand-Alone NR-RAN simulation) comprising of AMF and UPF components, of various Core-Networks present at each of the platforms, assumes the appropriate placement of LoadCore Agents standing as the end simulation/measurement points. In this case, LoadCore Agents are used to emulate the RAN(+UE) and the Public-Data-Network (PDN). Traffic is established via RAN attachment to the Core n/w, followed by UE registration and PDU session. The results of any given test in this configuration are collected using the LoadCore Middleware (MDW), after which they can be analyzed and processed by the experimenter.

The following schematic shows how LoadCore interconnects with the core under test.

Figure 2: LoadCore interconnection schematic

The LoadCore Agent simulating the RAN connects to the core's AMF through the N2 interface and the core's UPF through the N3 interface. The UPF is then connected to the agent simulating the DN through the N6 interface.

1.1.1.1 TEST CASE 1: TCP/HTTP TRAFFIC TESTS

Test Case 1 describes a setup where TCP traffic is pushed through each trial network configuration. This test case is split into two testing configurations, focusing on different KPIs, as described below. This test case category is performed with HTTP traffic over TCP Transport; with HTTP-GET as DL and HTTP-PUT as UL traffic. TCP transport provides flow-control and reliable delivery in a connection-oriented mechanism while using multiple connections. The user experiences the data rate at the application layer, which is served by the Application Server placed outside core in the PDN, the path involves multiple elements affecting the packet flow. The user doesn't need to take any action on any packet loss or jitter due to underlying network, TCP transport takes care of all. Using TCP transport for application-layer user-experienced data-rate evaluation provides for a sustained reliable performance measurement of throughput. TCP is also the most prominent transport protocol used by mobile applications.

1.1.1.2 TEST CASE 1.1: PEAK DATA RATE (PDR)

Test Case 1.1 is used to test the **Peak Data Rate (PDR)** KPI. To facilitate this, the best possible conditions are created on the network. Only one UE is connected and the number of active connections per UE has been increased to 10. A TCP throughput target of 5Gbps is set for both uplink and downlink as an "infinite" target, with both being run separately. This "infinite" throughput target is not expected to be achievable for any of the currently implemented trial networks due to the RAN limitations but is used to ensure that the highest possible data rate is experienced by the UE. This test is run for 2 hours.

Upon completion of the uplink and downlink runs the data is extracted and processed as described in Annex 1 – TCP Throughput Log Extraction and Analysis. The largest value here is noted as the **PDR**, and the 95th percentile value is also identified to provide some characterization of the top end of throughput results.

1.1.1.3 TEST CASE 1.2: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PACKET LOSS RATE(PLR)

Test Case 1.2 is used to test **User Experienced Data Rate (UEDR)** and **Packet Loss Rate (PLR)** KPIs. Once again, uplink and downlink are run as separate tests, with an uplink goal of 50Mbps and a downlink goal of 500Mbps. These values were agreed by the consortium as values that should be realistic and easily achievable by all deployed cores. This test case is run with multiple UEs, specifically .7, .8, .9 and 1x of the defined maximum UE load of a given trial network. This test is run for 1 hour.

Upon completion of all uplink and downlink runs, the data is extracted and processed as described in Annex 1 – TCP Throughput Log Extraction and Analysis. Additionally for this test case, all throughput values are divided by the number of UEs used in each test. The reason for this is that **UEDR** is measured on a per UE basis. While LoadCore does not record throughput data individually for all UEs, the fact that all the UEs to be used for these tests are either simulated or experiencing effectively identical network conditions means that dividing the total throughput by the amount of UEs is an effective way of visualizing the throughput per UE. The **UEDR** is then noted by finding the 5th percentile value in this dataset, with the peak throughput value also noted to better characterize the dataset.

The **PLR** is noted by leveraging the results presented within the LoadCore UI. In the Application Traffic screen in the Statistics page for a given test run, the "TCP" subsection presents details about the TCP traffic of a given test, including packet statistics such as packets sent, packets received, retransmissions, etc. Given the simple nature of this test case, it is enough to find difference between the packets sent and packets received to calculate this KPI. The packets received at the receiving interface is subtracted from the packets sent at the transmission interface, and this result is then converted to a percentage of the total number of packets sent. This value is the **PLR**.

1.1.1.4 TEST CASE 2: UDP TRAFFIC TESTS

Test Case 2 is used to test the **User Plane Latency (UPL)** and **Delay Deviation (DD)** KPIs. It describes a setup where UDP traffic is pushed through the target network topology. In this case, uplink and downlink are run simultaneously, with goals of 50Mbps and 500Mbps respectively. These values were agreed by the consortium as values that should be realistic and easily achievable by all deployed cores, considering the RAN constraints to be simulated. This test case is conducted with multiple UEs, specifically .7, .8, .9, and 1x of the defined maximum UE load of a given trial network. The duration of this test is one (1) hour. UDP is the choice of transport layer for this test category since latency/One-Way-Delay (OWD) and jitter evaluation is precise here. UDP uses a simple datagram, it's connectionless (so no establishment or handshake) and there is no acknowledgement mechanism hence it's fastest amongst other transport options and hence our choice.

Upon completion of all test runs, the LoadCore UI is leveraged to extract the KPIs. LoadCore records the One-Way Delay for both uplink and down link by sorting the delay for each packet into one of the following buckets: 0-125us, 125-250us, 250-500us, 500-1000us, 5-10ms, 10-15ms, 15-20ms, 20+ms. A running average for the delay is also calculated with every new packet. The **UPL** is recorded as a combination of this average value as well as the distribution of delay magnitudes. The **DD** is provided as the LoadCore's Delay Variation Jitter value. This value records the difference between the delay of two consecutive pairs of UDP packets and sorts them into buckets of the same sizes as the ones for the One-Way Delay measurement. Again, much like the One-Way Delay, a running average is calculated for the Delay Variation Jitter value for each new set of pairs of packets. The **DD** is recorded as a combination of this average value as well as the distribution of jitter magnitudes.

1.1.1.5 TEST CASE 3: UDP TRAFFIC TESTS WITH IDLE CYCLES

This test case describes a setup where UDP traffic is pushed through the system/software deployment under test and is used to measure the **Control Plane Latency (CPL)**. For this test, the **CPL** is measured as the time it takes a UE to go from idle to a state of transmission. To facilitate this, the "Enter/Exit Idle" secondary objective is enabled within the LoadCore control plane options. This option is used to cycle UEs in and out of an idle state. As it should not influence this test given the configuration, the throughput is set to a relatively low value of 500kbps to allow for easier postprocessing. This test is conducted with multiple UEs, specifically .7, .8, .9 and 1x of the defined maximum UE load of a given trial network. This test is run for 1 hour.

Test Case 3 uses a minimal UDP traffic, as the objective here is to measure the control plane and user plane interaction, so the actual application traffic nature is not material here. Each UE is set to cycle in and out of an idle state 200 times. The core is instructed to initiate these cycles at a per second rate equivalent to the maximum UE load of the given trial network, and each UE is set to maintain each transmit/idle state for 2 seconds.

The extraction of the **CPL** is done through the analysis of the packet capture data from the LoadCore RAN agent. Custom code is written for this purpose. The code takes as input the control and data plane captures from the agent and the number of UEs in each test. The code first identifies the IPs of each UE from within the captures, and then locates every instance of a packet which signifies that the UE is being instructed to exit an idle state. For each of these messages, the code then finds the first traffic packet from the corresponding UE that occurs directly after this instruction message. The time between these two packets is recorded. All these times are recorded, and an overall average is presented as the final **CPL** result.

1.1.1.6 TEST CASE 4: LONG DURATION AVAILABILITY TESTING – MIXED TRAFFIC

This test case describes a setup where multiple types of traffic are pushed through the setup over an extended period to measure the **Availability (AVL)**. The traffic types are selected to provide a realistic load on the network, ensuring it can withstand expected deployment conditions. The availability here is calculated as $1 - (\text{MTTR} / \text{MTBF}) * 100\%$, where MTTR is the mean time to repair and MTBF is the mean time between failures. . The test is

targeted to run for 170 hours. During the runtime, failures of the control plane, data throughput degradation and MOS decline are the observable events to determine if the network is running correctly.

The traffic mix used for this test contains Static Data Traffic TCP based HTTP, HTTPS, Video OTT traffic (HLS-HTTP and DASH-QUIC) and VoIP voice and video calls. This traffic is then divided over the max UE count in the following scheme:

- 70% of the UEs (14) perform static data & video OTT while entering and existing idle state, every 60 secs.
- 20% of the UEs (4) perform static-data, video OTT, VoIP voice while performing Xn based Handovers every 60 secs.
- 10% of the UEs (2) perform static-data, video OTT, VoIP voice-video while performing NG/N2-N3 based Handovers every 60 secs.

The video streams are 5400 seconds long and repeat over the entirety of the test duration. Voice calls are 90 seconds of TCP-3GPP IPSEC and Video calls are 120 seconds of TLS. Both also repeat for the entirety of the test duration. For HTTP/HTTPS traffic, 10 TCP connections per UE are configured. Static data is set to 100Mbps per UE and 2 * 1000Kbps of Video OTT DL streams.

The target length for this test case is set to 170 hours. However, due to limitations on testing time at any given platform, this was able to be shortened if necessary.

2.4 END-TO-END PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT METHODOLOGY

End to end performance measurement is envisaged using real UEs, in near perfect radio conditions, attached to NR-RAN which is in-turn connected to the NGC. IxChariot Endpoints installed as application in the UEs perform the traffic tests. Another Endpoint which is VM based, is placed on the PDN exit of the Core n/w. IxChariot MDW is the centralized Web UI based controller where the test is configured with traffic between Endpoints. Therefore, E2E as in UE to UE VoIP call/service KPI evaluation and UE to PDN as an E2E service topology are considered. Having a clear view at the system and software level from the core and data center perspective, adding the RAN equipment for end-to-end performance measurements provides not only a clear picture of the end-user experience, but also allows for investigating the impact of the various access network technologies against the baseline system-software performance as benchmarked in 2.2.

The end-to-end performance measurement has been conducted to one selected 5G+ deployment per platform as proposed per platform leader considering the most powerful radio-access system capabilities & relevant maturity. It is evident that for the end-to-end measurements the radio equipment nominal performance targets are decisive for the overall results, and as such, the results reported must be evaluated in conjunction to these targets.

2.4.1 MEASURING & TESTING TOOL

From the list of tools evaluated, Keysight IxChariot and Hawkeye are the most appropriate to collect measurements from the end-to-end perspective. Both tools are based on the same core design as described in Deliverable 5.1 [2], with the main difference being the format of generated results; Hawkeye gives results in a format more suited towards real-time monitoring, while IxChariot's results for reporting and analysis, making it a better fit for usage in this phase of testing. IxChariot tool uses probes connected to a central monitoring middleware to examine the end-to-end performance of a network, with the deployment architecture seen below. The tool runs as a UE application injecting mobile data traffic towards a VM sitting at the Destination Network (N6). Figure 3 shows how its Web-GUI represents the connectivity and test topology.

Figure 3: IxChariot Web- GUI Representation of the Test Topology

2.4.2 RELATED METRICS

The KPIs that are relevant for end-to-end measurements are presented in Table 2, together with the associated metrics and statistical post-processing (e.g., min/max/average) used to synthesize the reported results. This processing is performed transparently by the IxChariot application during the execution of the associated Test Case as detailed in Section 2.4.3 that follows.

Table 2: End-to-End Measurements for KPI Validation: Collected Metrics, Measurements & Test Cases

KPI	Metrics Collected	Measurements	Relevant Test Case
Peak Data Rate (PDR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Full Traffic Aggregate Max Data Rate (Mbps) 	1) Peak/Max Value	Test Case #5 – All Traffic
User Experienced Data Rate (UEDR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Full Traffic Data Rate Logs (Mbps) 	1) 5 th Percentile Value	Test Case #5 – All Traffic
Delay Deviation (DD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AMR WB - Average and Maximum Jitter values (ms) 	1) Average value of all samples 2) Peak value of all samples 3) Minimum value of all samples	Test Case #5 – AMR-WB
MOS Score (MOS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AMR WB – Average and Maximum MOS values 	1) Average Value of all samples 2) Peak value of all samples 3) Minimum value of all samples 4) Average R Value	Test Case #5 – AMR-WB

2.4.3 TEST SCOPE & TEST CASES

All 6G SANDBOX platforms have installed IxChariot and have configured the same test case for the collection of measurements which is described below. While the tool generates an extensive list of measurements for each KPI, simulating concurrent use of various user sessions and traffic flows (e.g., Voice, Data, Streaming, Browsing) that are available within the project's dataset repository (see Annexes), the most indicative diagrams are selectively presented in this document.

In this configuration, a real RAN is added to the baseline system/software configuration, LoadCore is not used. A real UE is attached to the Core N/w via the real RAN. IxChariot probes are brought in at either end of the network for end-to-end testing; with an App Endpoint at the UE and a VM Endpoint sitting at the PDN. The probes will generate traffic streams to send through the network and the results are collected using the IxChariot middleware, after which they can be analyzed and processed by the experimenter.

1.1.1.7 TEST CASE 5: E2E SERVICE KPI MEASUREMENTS

This Test Case is used to measure end-to-end sustained reliable DL data throughput performance (**Peak Data Rate** and **User Experienced Data Rate**) along with **Delay Deviation** and **MOS**. This throughput measurement is analogous to the internet-based speed-test applications, with the basic difference being that this is measured continuously for 1 hour. The test uses 8 Downlink TCP-HTTP connections for downlink throughput generation with 1 stream of bidirectional AMR-WB (Adaptive Multi-Rate Codec Wide-Band 23.85 Kbps) VoIP traffic. This AMR-WB-RTP-UDP traffic stream is used to measure **DD** and additionally voice **MOS** (Mean Optimum Score vide ITU-T T-REC-P.800.1) in the E2E topology from UE to PDN.

IxChariot produces both CSVs and an automatically generated report. The values for **Delay Deviation**, **MOS**, and **Peak Data Rate** are taken directly from this report, while the **User Experienced Data Rate** is calculated from the CSVs in the same way that this is done for Test Case 1.

3 ATHENS MEASUREMENT TOPOLOGIES AND RESULTS

3.1 SYSTEM/SOFTWARE LEVEL MEASUREMENTS

The Athens platform, spanning between the sites of OTE and NCSR D that are interconnected through a dedicated leased line, is flexible to support various 5G deployment options. Nonetheless, three distinct configurations are indicative to characterize its performance variations, depicting both the experimental and enterprise capabilities supported. Athens' platform leverages the capability to span in more than 22 Kms distance between the access and core networks, supporting both open-source and carrier grade infrastructure as described. Detailed description of the Athens platform infrastructure can be found in D4.1 [3] and the 6G-SANDBOX website³.

In all cases, there is one centrally deployed LoadCore MDW to manage the trial measurements:

- The Reference Trial Network, Open5GS with Centralized Agents: In this configuration, Open5GS is deployed at NCSR D, where both primary agents are located at the same site. The MDW is deployed separately at OTE.
- Enterprise (ATHONET) Trial Network: The third configuration utilizes the ATHONET Core, all including both LoadCore's RAN and DN agents as well as the MDW within OTE's cloud infrastructure.
- Open5GS/MOCN with Distributed Agents Trial Network: This setup also employs Open5GS, but it differentiates itself by distributing the network agents across the two sites, enhancing flexibility and scalability to simulate the MOCN setup developed in the Athens platform.

The datasets related to the tests performed for these configurations as described in the sections below are published in ZENODO, as detailed in ANNEX 2 – Athens Detailed Results.

3.1.1 REFERENCE TRIAL NETWORK

The network topology diagram in Figure 4 illustrates the configuration between the two Athens platform sites: NCSR D Premises and OTE Premises. At NCSR D Premises, LoadCore agents are integrated into the cloud infrastructure, with Agent 1 handling the Radio Access Network (RAN) and Agent 2 managing the Data Network (DN). Both agents operate on virtual machines, each with 2 CPUs and 4 GB of RAM. Additionally, the Open5GS User Plane (UP) and Control Plane (CP) are deployed at NCSR D Premises on separate virtual machines, each also equipped with 2 CPUs and 4 GB of RAM. In this setup, the LoadCore MDW is deployed at OTE Premises, so the interconnection of the components is achieved through the dedicated link of the dark fiber.

The NCSR D site leverages a PROXMOX server platform, which includes three Dell PowerEdge R350 servers. These servers provide a robust infrastructure, featuring a total storage capacity of 7.5 TB SSD, 1 TB SSD HA, and 384 GB of RAM, to support the virtualized network components. At the OTE premises, the LoadCore Middleware (MDW) is hosted on an HPE Proliant DL380 Gen10 server. This server is powered by 44 CPUs, specifically Intel Xeon Gold 6152 processors running at 2.10 GHz. The OTE site utilizes an ESXi server platform for virtualization. To ensure seamless connectivity and data transfer between the two sites, they are connected via a Dark Fiber link with a capacity of 10 Gbps. This high-speed connection is managed by 10G SFP+ CWDM ZR CRS Switches located at both ends, facilitating efficient and reliable communication between the NCSR D and OTE premises.

³ <https://6g-sandbox.eu/pilot-6g-sites/athens/>

Figure 4: Measurement Topology and setup for the Reference Trial Network in Athens platform

1.1.1.8 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

3.1.1.1.1 TEST CASE 1.1: PEAK DATA RATE(PDR)

Table 3:PDR Results for Athens Platform -Reference TN

DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
528,14	468,87	322,87	285,04

3.1.1.1.2 TEST CASE 1.2: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PACKET LOSS RATE(PLR)

Table 4: UEDR, PLR Results for Athens Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	DL UEDR (Mbps)	DL Peak (Mbps)	DL PLR	UL UEDR (Mbps)	UL Peak (Mbps)	UL PLR
14	21,42	35,41	0,56%	3,39	3,96	8,36%
16	19,39	29,94	0,82%	2,96	3,44	8,99%
18	15,94	26,89	1,08%	2,62	3,14	9,73%
20	14,02	23,56	1,34%	2,35	2,84	10,31%

3.1.1.1.3 TEST CASE 2: USER PLANE LATENCY(UPL), DELAY DEVIATION(DD)

Table 5: UPL, DD Results for Athens Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	DL Average UPL (ms)	UL Average UPL (ms)	DL Average DD (ms)	UL Average DD (ms)
14	27,03	8,09	1,07	2,63
16	27,04	8,43	1,20	2,93
18	26,81	8,47	1,30	3,11
20	27,15	8,76	1,43	3,38

Considering the distribution of the UPL values observed, Figure 5 and Figure 6 depict the UPL value ranges for Uplink and Downlink, and Figure 7, Figure 8 respectively for DD values distribution, during the test case execution involving the maximum number of UEs (20 UEs). Analytical data, for the respective distributions of the executions with 14, 16, 18 and 20 UEs, including the exact number of samples collected per value range can be found in the ANNEX 2 – Athens Detailed Results.

Figure 5: Downlink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-Reference TN

Figure 6: Uplink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-Reference TN

Figure 7: Downlink DD Distribution for Athens platform-Reference TN

Figure 8: Uplink DD Distribution for Athens platform-Reference TN

3.1.1.1.4 TEST CASE 3: CONTROL PLANE LATENCY(CPL)

Table 6: CPL Results for Athens Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	Average CPL (ms)
14	249,4
16	291,2
18	324,3
20	372,8

3.1.1.1.5 TEST CASE 4: AVAILABILITY(AVL)

Test Case 4 in Athens was run for 68 hours without any disruptions or downtime occurring. This can be seen in Figure 9, in two ways: in the first row by noticing that there are no SCTP abortions from the LoadCore agents, and by noticing a constant data flow during the duration of the tests in the subsequent diagrams, nonetheless within a constrained time window, as captured in the dashboard.

Figure 9: Availability Results for Athens Platform – Reference TN

3.1.2 ENTERPRISE (ATHONET) TRIAL NETWORK

The enterprise deployment of ATHONET is the second “configuration” for the Athens platform. Figure 10 below illustrates the topology and the interconnection between the LoadCore tool and the ATHONET 5GC SA. The left server hosts the LoadCore MDW, responsible for collecting results during measurements, as well as two agents responsible for emulating the RAN and DN. The infrastructure utilizes an HPE ProLiant DL380 Gen10 server, featuring 44 CPUs powered by Intel Xeon Gold 6152 processors, each operating at 2.10 GHz. The server runs ESXi for virtualization, providing a stable and flexible environment for running the virtual machines (VMs) required by the three different components.

Figure 10: Measurement Topology and setup for the Enterprise (ATHONET) Trial Network in Athens platform (all in OTE site)

The right part of the figure depicts the infrastructure where ATHONET's 5G SA core network is deployed. This setup is powered by an HPE ProLiant DL385 Gen10 server, which offers 488 vCPUs, providing substantial processing power to handle the high computational demands of the 5G core network. It also includes 576 GB of RAM, supporting memory-intensive operations and ensuring smooth performance, and 4 TB of storage, accommodating extensive data storage requirements. The server runs on Red Hat Cloud Infrastructure, offering

a scalable and flexible cloud environment that enhances the network's agility and reliability. The two servers are interconnected through an Aruba 3810M-16SFP+ 2-slot switch. This high-performance switch supports SFP+ ports, enabling 10 Gbps connectivity, which is crucial for the different subnets to reach each other.

1.1.1.9 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

3.1.2.1.1 TEST CASE 1.1: PEAK DATA RATE(PDR)

Table 7: PDR Results for Athens Platform -ATHONET TN

DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
940,05	938,53	935	934,73

3.1.2.1.2 TEST CASE 1.2: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PACKET LOSS RATE(PLR)

Table 8: UEDR, PLR Results for Athens Platform -ATHONET TN

Number of UEs	DL UEDR (Mbps)	DL Peak (Mbps)	DL PLR	UL UEDR (Mbps)	UL Peak (Mbps)	UL PLR
14	35,19	36,43	0,00%	3	3,32	0,05%
16	30,89	32,5	0,00%	3,08	3,2	0,00%
18	27,35	28,27	0,00%	2,58	2,75	0,05%
20	24,61	25,5	0,00%	2,46	2,61	0,00%

3.1.2.1.3 TEST CASE 2: USER PLANE LATENCY(UPL), DELAY DEVIATION(DD)

Table 9: UPL, DD Results for Athens Platform -ATHONET TN

Number of UEs	DL Average UPL (ms)	UL Average UPL (ms)	DL Average DD (ms)	UL Average DD (ms)
14	0,43	0,22	0,07	0,05
16	0,45	0,21	0,10	0,06
18	0,42	0,22	0,12	0,06
20	0,43	0,22	0,12	0,06

Considering the distribution of the UPL values observed, Figure 11 and Figure 12 depict the UPL value ranges for Uplink and Downlink, and Figure 13, Figure 14 respectively for DD values distribution, during the test case execution involving the maximum number of UEs (20 UEs). Analytical data, for the respective distributions of the executions with 14, 16, 18 and 20 UEs, including the exact number of samples collected per value range can be found in the ANNEX 2 – Athens Detailed Results.

Figure 11: Downlink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-ATHONET TN

Figure 12: Uplink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-ATHONET TN

Figure 13: Downlink DD Distribution for Athens platform-ATHONET TN

Figure 14: Uplink DD Distribution for Athens platform-ATHONET TN

3.1.2.1.4 TEST CASE 3: CONTROL PLANE LATENCY(CPL)

Table 10: CPL Results for Athens Platform -ATHONET TN

Number of UEs	Average CPL(s)
14	238,0
16	382,1
18	245,7
20	359,3

3.1.3 OPEN5GS/MOCN – DISTRIBUTED AGENTS DEPLOYMENT TRIAL NETWORK

The third configuration is distinguished from the reference trial network (section 5.1.2) by the strategic distribution of agents across two sites, while keeping the rest of the infrastructure resources the same.

At the OTE premises, the HPE ProLiant DL380 server running ESXi hosts critical components such as the LoadCore MDW and the VM responsible for the RAN agent. In contrast, at the NCSR premises, the agent responsible for emulating the DN (Data Network) is deployed within a Proxmox environment. This setup also hosts the CP and UP VMs for the Open5GS system, each allocated 4 CPUs and 4 GB of RAM. The Dell PowerEdge R530 server, managed by Proxmox, provides the necessary computational resources to support.

By distributing the agents across the two sites, this configuration optimizes resource utilization and potentially enhances performance through role separation. The OTE premises handle the demanding tasks of LoadCore MDW and the RAN agent with the efficiency of ESXi, while the NCSR premises utilize Proxmox to manage the CP and UP VMs for Open5GS and the DN emulation agent, ensuring a balanced and efficient network infrastructure.

Figure 15: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Open5GS/MOCN Trial Network in Athens platform

1.1.1.10 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

3.1.3.1.1 TEST CASE 1.1: PEAK DATA RATE(PDR)

Table 11: PDR Results for Athens Platform - Open5GS/MOCN TN

DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
445,23	359,96	338,78	247,02

3.1.3.1.2 TEST CASE 1.2: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PACKET LOSS RATE(PLR)

Table 12:EUDR, PLR Results for Athens Platform - Open5GS/MOCN TN

Number of UEs	DL UEDR (Mbps)	DL Peak (Mbps)	DL PLR	UL UEDR (Mbps)	UL Peak (Mbps)	UL PLR
14	8,3	29,89	0,64%	3,31	4,12	8,31%
16	7,08	25,89	0,95%	2,9	3,65	9,01%
18	6,05	22,05	1,22%	2,58	3,24	9,47%
20	3,49	14,23	9,70%	2,3	2,87	9,86%

3.1.3.1.3 TEST CASE 2: USER PLANE LATENCY(UPL), DELAY DEVIATION(DD)

Table 13: UPL, DD Results for Athens Platform - Open5GS/MOCN TN

Number of UEs	DL Average UPL (ms)	UL Average UPL (ms)	DL Average DD (ms)	UL Average DD (ms)
14	33,53	10,14	0,94	2,85
16	33,87	10,30	1,01	3,04
18	33,56	10,14	1,09	3,23
20	33,92	11,07	1,19	3,71

Considering the distribution of the UPL values observed, Figure 16 and Figure 17 depict the UPL value ranges for Uplink and Downlink, and Figure 18, Figure 19 respectively for DD values distribution, during the test case execution involving the maximum number of UEs (20 UEs). Analytical data, for the respective distributions of the executions with 14, 16, 18 and 20 UEs, including the exact number of samples collected per value range can be found in the ANNEX 2 – Athens Detailed Results.

Figure 16: Downlink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-Open5GS/MOCN TN Figure 17: Uplink UPL Distribution for Athens platform-Open5GS/MOCN TN

Figure 18: Downlink DD Distribution for Athens platform-Open5GS/MOCN TN Figure 19: Uplink DD Distribution for Athens platform-Open5GS/MOCN TN

3.1.3.1.4 TEST CASE 3: CONTROL PLANE LATENCY(CPL)

Table 14: CPL Results for Athens Platform - Open5GS/MOCN TN

Number of UEs	Average CPL(ms)
14	231,9
16	247,1
18	275,6
20	314,6

3.2 END-2-END MEASUREMENTS

3.2.1 ENTERPRISE (ATHONET) TRIAL NETWORK

As the Athens platform accommodates various 5GCs and RAN configurations, for the end-to-end performance measurements, the ATHONET 5GC and Ericsson RAN have been selected. The diagram in Figure 20 details the network topology and configuration employed on the Athens platform for these measurements using the Ixchariot tool. This configuration has been designed using the most optimal radio access capacity and resources utilization, thereby enhancing the efficiency and precision of the performance assessment.

In this setup, two endpoints (UEs) Xiaomi 12 Pro with Cortex-A510 and Huawei P40 Pro with Cortex-A55, communicate with the Ericsson 4408 gNB via both uplink and downlink channels. The gNB is connected to the BBU 6630, which is integrated with the IRU Controller 8848, as it also supports indoor dots. The BBU processes signals from the gNB and interfaces with the core network of ATHONET, hosted on an HPE ProLiant DL385 Gen10 server with 48 vCPUs, 576 GB of RAM, and 4 TB of storage, running on Red Hat Cloud Infrastructure. The Ixchariot server (hosted as a VM on an HPE ProLiant DL380 ESXi server) initiates the performance test by generating synthetic traffic towards the UE which acts as the endpoint. The IxChariot APK file was deemed necessary to be installed on the UE to utilize IxChariot's network performance testing capabilities directly on the device.

Figure 20: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Enterprise (ATHONET) Trial Network in Athens platform

The configurations for the radio are presented in Table 3 below:

Table 15: Athens Platform Radio Configuration for End-to-End Measurements

Band	n78, ARFCN 636666, 3500 MHz
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	100 MHz
Carrier-Components	1 carrier
MIMO-layer	4T1R
DL MIMO Mode	4X4
Subcarrier-spacing	30 KHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	DDDSUDDDD

1.1.1.11 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

3.2.1.1.1 TEST CASE 5: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PEAK DATA RATE(PDR), DELAY DEVIATION(DD), MOS SCORES(MOSS)

Table 16:PDR, UEDR End-to-End Results for Athens Platform

KPI	Value (Mbps)
PDR	980,43
UEDR	937,96

Figure 21: Min/Max/Avg Throughput for Athens platform – end-to-end

Delay Deviation through the IxCharriot tool was not able to be reported on this deployment. Instead, other indicative end to end measurements through UE Android applications measuring latency (ICMP) and speedtest are presented in the figures below.

Figure 22: Athens End-to-End ICMP Measurements

Figure 23: Athens End-to-End Speed Test Measurements

Table 17: MOS End-to-End Results for Athens Platform

KPI	Value
MOS - Average	4,17
MOS - Max	4,15
MOS - Min	3,02
MOS – Average R Value	82,53

3.3 ASSURANCE TESTING

6G-SANDBOX Trial Networks will need to be able to be deployed for extended periods of time and retain their performance throughout the entirety of said period. As such, a subset of the tests performed throughout this report were repeated later, closer to this reports submission to check the consistency of the results and increase the statistical confidence of the results provided. The results for these assurance tests (reported vs. repeated values) for the Athens platform are reported below.

Table 18: Assurance Testing Results for Athens Platform

Results	DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
Reported	528,14	468,87	322,87	285,04
Repeated	457,5	416,76	274,10	250,27
Delta	13,35%	11,11%	15,11%	12,20%

3.4 RESULT ANALYSIS

The Athens platform has tested two different 5G SA Core solutions, Open5GS and ATHONET, that were installed in different physical and virtualized infrastructures. It has also tested the same core solution (Open5GS) under two different layouts in respect to the UE/RAN agent placement, to deduce the impact of the transport connection in the performance measurements. The latter is important as part of the 6G SANDOX activities in Athens include the configuration of MOCN (Multi-Operator Core Network) that would allow the flexible use of RAN equipment among OTE and NCSR core sites, to better support the experimentation demands.

Briefing on the results of the **first deployment**, the reference Open5GS TN, the PDR, UPL and DD values reached are notably low, considering that both the source and destination endpoints (the LoadCore agents) and Open5GS were collocated, and the test case had been dimensioned to achieve an infinite (5Gbps) max value. Evidently, the limitations lie in the hosting infrastructure. Towards this direction one striking point is that the deployment of Open5GS in Athens followed the cloud native paradigm of implementing the 5GC as a microservice based architecture thus adding various abstraction layers with performance cost. In this setup the Network Functions (NFs) are standalone containers with the necessary dependencies, including protocols signaling etc. on top of the virtualization layer. Furthermore, the selection of Proxmox as the hosting environment, being an open platform for efficient management of virtualization resources, even though valuable for administration

purposes, proves not efficient in terms of performance. Overall, this type of implementation, including containerization and manageability on top of virtualization, appears to impact the overall performance, which is an important finding to be considered during the next round of measurements. The way forward to bridge the performance gap is to migrate Open5GS to a leaner deployment, leveraging the optimized virtualization environment of OpenNebula (ONE), and following the setup as standardized by the project TN specifications.

Crosschecking the results with the **third deployment**, still measuring the same Open5GS installation, but incurring the overhead of the transport network by placing the UE/RAN agent at the OTE site interconnected through a 20Km-long fiber link with the core installation at NCSR D, we can determine the relevant performance impact for multi-sited/distributed experiments. In this setup, there is a physical constraint of 1 Gbps, incurred by the Mikrotik router handling the direct interconnection at the NCSR D site. Another parameter to be considered is the hosting of the agent in an ESXi server not only at a different physical host from the 5G Core but also in a different data center, therefore time synchronization issues (same clock reference) need to be investigated and addressed. The impact of these changes is seen as a 24% decrease in the most experienced (95th percentile) DL PDR and 15% in the UL PDR respectively. Interestingly, the average measurements per UE in respect to DL UEDR seem to be more severely affected (i.e., for 20 UEs in the collocated environment of the first deployment the average UEDR was 14,02 Mbps per UE while the equivalent for the distributed third deployment had been just 3,48Mbps per UE). In respect to UPL (both UL and DL) a constant 20% increase is observed, while the Average DD remains approximately the same for both deployments. The impact of the distributed setup for CPL varies in the range of 8%-15%. A notable update in the deployment to increase the performance is the replacement of the 1Gbps network router and SFPs across the Athens direct-link interconnection with 10G equipment.

The **second deployment** focuses on a carrier-grade core deployment of the ATHONET 5GC on a ten (10)-node on-premises Redhat Openstack cloud. An important observation for the measurement topology is that both the UE/RAN and DN agents are not collocated with the 5G core as in the rest topologies but are hosted as two (2) VMs in an ESXi server, interconnected through a complicated Layer-3 physical and virtual networking with the Redhat cloud. The PDR values observed both for UL and DL (940 Mbps and 935 Mbps respectively), reach the physical constraint of the network interfaces of the VMs of the LoadCore agents, that were set to 1Gbps, and are thus considered satisfactory. For UEDR measurements, having in mind that the LoadCore tool constraints the generated traffic by simulating the RAN behavior to 50Mbps UL and 500 Mbps DL, it can be noticed that in all cases the nominal value is practically reached (e.g., for 20UEs, with 24,61 Mbps DL per UE the aggregate DL becomes 493 Mbps against the 500 Mbps target, and similarly for UL the aggregated UL is 49,2 Mbps against 50 Mbps target). In respect to the DL UPL values of 0,4 ms are steadily observed, and for respectively for UL UPL 0,2 ms. Considering that these measurements incorporate the network latency between the UE/RAN, 5G core, DN nodes, the results are well accepted.

Overall, the reported CPL values, that are heavily impacted by the LoadCore processing logic to simulate 5G control plane interactions, are statistically the same as all the rest 5G SANDBOX tested configurations.

In respect to the end-to-end measurements, considering that there are limitations set by the RAN product, where the DL data bit rate in ideal conditions is not expected to exceed 1,2 Gbps and 100 Mbps for UL respectively according to the vendor's specifications, the results are satisfactory. When compared to the LoadCore measurements the throughput results are similar, and especially when comparing user plane latency for the data traffic (end-to-end measurements ranging from 10ms to 25ms when at system/software level less than 0,5ms) the impact of the RAN becomes obvious.

4 BERLIN MEASUREMENT TOPOLOGIES AND RESULTS

4.1 SYSTEM/SOFTWARE LEVEL MEASUREMENTS

The 6G-SANDBOX platform can support a variety of trial networks through the infrastructure capabilities reported in D4.1 [3] and the 6G-SANDBOX website⁴. The Berlin Platform uses two Hypervisor environments with a different set of servers to implement three different test configurations. The first configuration using Open5GS is the Reference setup like in the other platforms. The second and the third configuration uses Fraunhofer FOKUS own developed Open5Gcore as the 5G core network. The ESXi Hypervisor is used to host the LoadCore and IxChariot middleware components in all the configurations. It is also shared with other Projects and used to host random other testbed services. The Placement of the 5G core and LoadCore agents is adapted for the different configurations, in particular:

- Reference Trial Network, Open5GS: In this configuration the Open5GS is deployed together with the LoadCore agents on the ESXi cluster. They are connected via virtual switches and cluster internal 10 GBit networking.
- Open5Gcore on ESXi Trial Network: The second configuration utilizes the Open5Gcore developed by FOKUS deployed on the ESXi cluster and the LoadCore agents deployed on the OpenNebula cluster. The Individual servers are interconnected via 10 and 100 GBit SDN switches.
- Open5Gcore on ONE Trial Network: The Third configuration uses the OpenNebula to deploy the LoadCore agents and the Open5gCore alongside in the same cluster. The individual servers are connected using 10Gbit links and ONE managed Linux Bridges. The setup was adapted with an VLAN to VXLAN translation VM because of performance issues.

The datasets related to the tests performed for these configurations as described in the sections below are published in ZENODO, as detailed in ANNEX 3 – Berlin Detailed Results.

4.1.1 REFERENCE TRIAL NETWORK

The diagram in Figure 24 represents the reference setup in Berlin platform. It utilizes the 6 servers of the VMware ESX cluster to host Open5GS and LoadCore agents and LoadCore MDW as separated virtual machines under the ESXi hypervisor.

As 5G core, a complete instantiation of Open5GS including User Plan (UP) and Control Plane (CP) is installed in a single VM. This VM is equipped with 4 CPUs and 4GB of RAM. On the other hand, two additional VMs, each one for a LoadCore agent, are equipped with 4 CPUs and 8 GB of RAM. These two LoadCore agents are used for Data Network and RAN, respectively. The LoadCore MDW is installed in another virtual machine with 8 CPUs and 24GB of RAM. The placement of the individual VMs is automatically decided by the VMWare vCenter manager based on the utilization of the 6 different servers in the cluster. The servers in the blade center are interconnected with multiple 10G interfaces using an internal switch which is then uplinked via two 20G links into the Cisco ACI fabric. The interconnection between blade center and ACI fabric does not affect the test as the data flow will only happen between the servers of the blade center where the Open5GS and LoadCore agents are hosted.

⁴ <https://6g-sandbox.eu/pilot-6g-sites/berlin/>

Figure 24: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Reference Trial Network in Berlin platform

1.1.1.12 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

4.1.1.1.1 TEST CASE 1.1: PEAK DATA RATE(PDR)

Table 19: PDR Results for Berlin Platform -Reference TN

DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
1297,36	1199,41	1039,01	996,07

4.1.1.1.2 TEST CASE 1.2: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PACKET LOSS RATE(PLR)

Table 20: : UEDR, PLR Results for Berlin Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	DL UEDR (Mbps)	DL Peak (Mbps)	DL PLR	UL UEDR (Mbps)	UL Peak (Mbps)	UL PLR
14	35,22	36,77	0,82%	3,42	3,98	8,38%
16	30,84	32,27	1,26%	2,98	3,46	9,11%
18	27,4	28,84	1,64%	2,65	3,12	9,03%
20	24,68	25,69	1,97%	2,38	2,76	9,56%

4.1.1.1.3 TEST CASE 2: USER PLANE LATENCY(UPL), DELAY DEVIATION(DD)

Table 21: UPL, DD Results for Berlin Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	DL Average UPL (ms)	UL Average UPL (ms)	DL Average DD (ms)	UL Average DD (ms)
14	0,47	0,19	0,11	0,07
16	0,45	0,19	0,07	0,06
18	0,46	0,18	0,06	0,06
20	0,45	0,21	0,10	0,08

Considering the distribution of the UPL values observed, Figure 25 and Figure 26 depict the UPL value ranges for Uplink and Downlink, and Figure 27, Figure 28 respectively for DD values distribution, during the test case execution involving the maximum number of UEs (20 UEs). Analytical data, for the respective distributions of the executions with 14, 16, 18 and 20 UEs, including the exact number of samples collected per value range can be found in the ANNEX 3 – Berlin Detailed Results.

Figure 25: Downlink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform-Reference TN

Figure 26: Uplink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform-Reference TN

Figure 27: Downlink DD Distribution for Berlin platform-Reference TN

Figure 28: Uplink DD Distribution for Berlin platform-Reference TN

4.1.1.1.4 TEST CASE 3: CONTROL PLANE LATENCY(CPL)

Table 22: CPL Results for Berlin Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	Average CPL (ms)
14	221,2
16	247,1
18	263,2
20	283,9

4.1.1.1.5 TEST CASE 4: AVAILABILITY(AVL)

Test Case 4 in Berlin was run for 170 hours without any unexpected disruptions or downtime occurring, apart from two occurrences that were associated with known maintenance actions. This can be seen in Figure 29, in two ways: in the first row by noticing that there are two known SCTP abortions from the LoadCore agents, and by noticing a constant data flow during the duration of the tests in the subsequent diagrams, nonetheless within a constrained time window, as captured in the dashboard.

Figure 29: Availability Results for Berlin Platform – Reference TN

4.1.2 ESXi OPEN5GCORE TRIAL NETWORK

The diagram in Figure 30 represents the second configuration of the Berlin platform which includes the Open5Gcore core network installed with CP and UP in a single virtual machine on the ESXi hypervisor. This VM is equipped with 4 CPU and 4 GB of RAM. The UPF of the Open5Gcore is configured to use the XDP data path acceleration to optimize the user plane data forwarding.

The two LoadCore agent virtual machines are equipped with 4 CPU and 4 GB of RAM. They are this time hosted on the OpenNebula (ONE) KVM hypervisor as this is the agreed Hypervisor for the 6G-Sandbox Sites. This Trial network layout will span across different hypervisors and will utilize the Cisco ACI Fabric switches. In particular the connection between ONE and ESXi servers is passing over a 10 G link to a Leaf switch then via 100G via a spine switch to another Leaf switch and then via 20G into the ESXi. The test user-data will flow two times over the network fabric, from the first agent via the 5g core into the other agent. The agents on ONE are connected to VXLAN and VLAN based trial networks, however the ESXi only supports VLAN. During the development of the test scenarios a performance issue was discovered when VXLAN based network separation was used with the LoadCore agent VMs on ONE hypervisor. The agents were configured to use VLAN networks to work around this performance issue and because the ESXi anyway uses VLAN based networks.

Figure 30: Measurement Topology & Setup for the ESXi Open5gCore Trial Network in Berlin platform

1.1.1.13 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

4.1.2.1.1 TEST CASE 1.1: PEAK DATA RATE(PDR)

Table 23: PDR Results for Berlin Platform -ESXi Open5gCore TN

DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
2394,18	2142,64	2188	2135,8

4.1.2.1.2 TEST CASE 1.2: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PACKET LOSS RATE(PLR)

Table 24: UEDR, PLR Results for Berlin Platform -ESXi Open5gCore TN

Number of UEs	DL UEDR (Mbps)	DL Peak (Mbps)	DL PLR	UL UEDR (Mbps)	UL Peak (Mbps)	UL PLR
14	35,04	36,78	0,01%	3,5	3,9	0,00%
16	30,66	32,23	0,05%	3,07	3,42	0,00%
18	27,26	28,69	0,10%	2,72	3,03	0,00%
20	24,52	25,93	0,16%	2,45	2,73	0,00%

4.1.2.1.3 TEST CASE 2: USER PLANE LATENCY(UPL), DELAY DEVIATION(DD)

Table 25: UPL, DD Results for Berlin Platform -ESXi Open5gCore TN

Number of UEs	DL Average UPL (ms)	UL Average UPL (ms)	DL Average DD (ms)	UL Average DD (ms)
14	0,21	0,19	0,06	0,04
16	0,22	0,19	0,03	0,03
18	0,23	0,19	0,05	0,06
20	0,25	0,18	0,06	0,03

Considering the distribution of the UPL values observed, Figure 31 and Figure 32 depict the UPL value ranges for Uplink and Downlink, and Figure 33, Figure 34 respectively for DD values distribution, during the test case execution involving the maximum number of UEs (20 UEs). Analytical data, for the respective distributions of the executions with 14, 16, 18 and 20 UEs, including the exact number of samples collected per value range can be found in the ANNEX 3 – Berlin Detailed Results.

Figure 31: Downlink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform-ESXi Open5GCore TN Figure 32: Uplink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform- ESXi Open5GCore TN

Figure 33: Downlink DD Distribution for Berlin platform- ESXi Open5GCore TN Figure 34: Uplink DD Distribution for Berlin platform- ESXi Open5GCore TN

4.1.2.1.4 TEST CASE 3: CONTROL PLANE LATENCY(CPL)

Table 26: CPL Results for Berlin Platform -ESXi Open5gCore TN

Number of UEs	Average CPL (ms)
14	215,7
16	243,4
18	263,2
20	283,9

4.1.3 ONE OPEN5GCORE TRIAL NETWORK

The third configuration of the Berlin platform that is shown in Figure 35 uses again the Open5Gcore Core network hosted on the ONE hypervisor. The main difference to the second configuration is that the LoadCore agents are also hosted as virtual machines on the same ONE hypervisor. The VM of the Open5gCore is equipped with 4 CPU and 4 GB of RAM.

The LoadCore agent VMs are each equipped with 4 CPU and 4 GM of RAM. The actual placement of the VMs is dynamically decided by the ONE hypervisor based on the load of the underlying servers.

The core VM uses VXLAN based networks for the connection towards the RAN and DN agents as this is the default for 6g-sandbox Trial networks. As described earlier the ONE platform does support VLAN and VXLAN virtual networks which differ by the overhead that is used to manage the encapsulation in regard of complexity and occupied extra bytes in each packet. During pre-test it was noticed that the LoadCore VM that used VXLAN based networks suffer from a significant performance issue of the factor of 4 to 5 on the Berlin platform hardware. The reasons for this have still to be figured out. The LoadCore VMs were configured to use VLAN based virtual networks to work around this performance issue. From the Hypervisor perspective the VLAN and VXLAN based networks are completely separated virtual networks which are not interconnected. To allow communication between the VXLAN and VLAN variant of the n2 n3 and n6 networks a separated VM was used. This bridge VM has 3 CPU and 512 MB of RAM and uses the Linux kernel L2 ethernet bridges to interconnect the virtual networks. Traffic flow of the Trial network will pass from the source agent via the Cisco ACI via the bridge VM across the 5gCore VM to the target agent VM. Depending on the placement of the VMs server-internal data paths or external 10Gbit links are used.

Figure 35: Measurement Topology & Setup for the ONE Open5gCore Trial Network in Berlin platform

1.1.1.14 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

4.1.3.1.1 TEST CASE 1.1: PEAK DATA RATE(PDR)

Table 27: PDR Results for Berlin Platform -ONE Open5gCore TN

DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
1029,74	996,91	1359,27	1243,04

4.1.3.1.2 TEST CASE 1.2: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PACKET LOSS RATE(PLR)

Table 28: UEDR, PLR Results for Berlin Platform -ONE Open5gCore TN

Number of UEs	DL UEDR (Mbps)	DL Peak (Mbps)	DL PLR	UL UEDR (Mbps)	UL Peak (Mbps)	UL PLR
14	35,36	36,85	0,00%	3,51	3,88	0,00%
16	30,9	32,53	0,03%	3,07	3,4	0,00%
18	27,35	28,77	0,11%	2,73	3,02	0,00%
20	24,69	25,82	0,52%	2,45	2,73	0,00%

4.1.3.1.3 TEST CASE 2: USER PLANE LATENCY(UPL), DELAY DEVIATION(DD)

Table 29: UPL, DD Results for Berlin Platform -ONE Open5gCore TN

Number of UEs	DL Average UPL (ms)	UL Average UPL (ms)	DL Average DD (ms)	UL Average DD (ms)
14	0,41	0,46	0,00	0,00
16	0,40	0,45	0,04	0,06
18	0,46	0,46	0,04	0,07
20	0,43	0,46	0,04	0,06

Considering the distribution of the UPL values observed, Figure 36 and Figure 37 depict the UPL value ranges for Uplink and Downlink, and Figure 38, Figure 39 respectively for DD values distribution, during the test case execution involving the maximum number of UEs (20 UEs). Analytical data, for the respective distributions of

the executions with 14, 16, 18 and 20 UEs, including the exact number of samples collected per value range can be found in the ANNEX 3 – Berlin Detailed Results.

Figure 36: Downlink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform- ONE Open5GCore TN

Figure 37: Uplink UPL Distribution for Berlin platform- ONE Open5GCore TN

Figure 38: Downlink DD Distribution for Berlin platform- ONE Open5GCore TN

Figure 39: Uplink DD Distribution for Berlin platform- ONE Open5GCore TN

4.1.3.1.4 TEST CASE 3: CONTROL PLANE LATENCY(CPL)

Table 30: CPL Results for Berlin Platform -ONE Open5gCore TN

Number of UEs	Average CPL (ms)
14	238,0
16	382,1
18	247,5
20	359,3

4.2 END-TO-END MEASUREMENTS

4.2.1 OPEN5GCORE TRIAL NETWORK

As the Berlin platform accommodates Open5GS and Open5Gcore and various RAN configurations, for the end-to-end performance measurements, the Open5Gcore on ESXi and Huawei RAN have been selected. The diagram in Figure 40 details the network topology and configuration employed on the Berlin platform for these measurements using the IxChariot tool. This configuration has been selected to provide optimal performance while being comparable to the previously described LoadCore measurements.

The setup uses a Samsung S21+ and a Samsung S23+ mobile phone as UE endpoints for the IxChariot tests. The phones are connected to a Huawei LampSite gNodeB made of a pRRU 5935 indoor Pico Radio Head connected to a RHUB 5923 and a BBU 5900. The radio equipment is interconnected using 10G eCIPRI Fiber links. The BBU is connected via 10G fiber links to the ESXi cluster which hosts the Open5Gcore similar to the second configuration used in the previous (LoadCore) tests. The ESXi cluster consists of 6 UCSB-200-M5 Blade servers with dual 32 core Xeon Gold 6130 CPUs and 256 GB of RAM where the 5G core VM is configured to have 4 CPU and 4 GB of RAM. The IxChariot Middleware and the N6-DN Endpoint are deployed alongside the 5gcore as a VM on the same ESXi cluster. The Endpoint is configured to have 2 CPU and 1 GB of RAM and the middleware uses 1 CPU and 2 GB of RAM. The following Figure 40 shows the details of the end-to-end setup.

Figure 40: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Open5Gcore e2e Trial Network in Berlin platform

The following Table lists the configuration parameters of the Radio Heads used for the end-to-end test.

Table 31: Berlin Platform Radio Configuration for End-to-End Measurements

Band	n78, ARFCN 650016, 3700 MHz
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	100 MHz 23dBm
Carrier-Components	1 carrier
MIMO-layer	4T4R
DL MIMO Mode	4x4
Subcarrier-spacing	30 KHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	4:1 DDDSU

1.1.1.15 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

4.2.1.1.1 TEST CASE 5: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PEAK DATA RATE(PDR), DELAY DEVIATION(DD), MOS SCORES(MOSS)

Table 32: PDR, UEDR End-to-End Results for Berlin Platform

KPI	Value (Mbps)
PDR	1200,10
UEDR	743,45

Figure 41:End-to-End Throughput Measurements for Berlin Platform

Table 33: DD End-to-End Results for Berlin Platform

KPI	Value (ms)
DD - Average	7,48
DD - Max	13
DD - Min	2

Table 34: MOS End-to-End Results for Berlin Platform

KPI	Value
MOS - Average	4,14
MOS - Max	4,15
MOS - Min	3,23
MOS – Average R Value	83,18

4.3 ASSURANCE TESTING

6G-SANDBOX Trial Networks will need to be able to be deployed for extended periods of time and retain their performance throughout the entirety of said period. As such, a subset of the tests performed throughout this report were repeated later closer to this reports submission to check the consistency of the results and increase the statistical confidence of the results provided. The results for these assurance tests (reported vs. repeated values) for the Berlin platform are reported below.

Table 35: Assurance Testing Results for Berlin Platform

Results	DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
Reported	1297,36	1199,41	1039,0	996,07
Repeated	1254,96	1224,56	1033,12	989,69
Delta	3,27%	2,10%	0,57%	0,64%

4.4 RESULT ANALYSIS

Overall, the results for the different configurations measured in the Berlin platform show good results after some performance issues were identified and worked around. One important performance issue that was found is that the LoadCore agents behave very differently (performance wise) depending on the virtual network encapsulation technology used. Test during the setup of the actual test configurations showed that when the agents were using VXLAN networks on the OpenNebula servers in Berlin the performance was 5 to 6 times slower compared to VLAN based networks. The root cause of this still has to be investigated, however it could be related to the age of the CPU's involved in the ONE servers. As the underlying network type did not have such an impact on the 5G-Core VMs it could also be possible that the optimized network stack of the Ixia agent is causing side effects on the VXLAN encapsulation. Instead of switching the complete test setup to VLAN based networks a bridging VM was introduced to keep as many of the components on VXLAN and just use VLAN for the agents. This additional VM might have a small impact on the latency and jitter, but we wanted to keep as much VXLAN as possible as this is the default virtual networking type for 6G-Sandbox. The differences between the two hypervisor platforms are mainly caused by the different generations of CPUs used in the underlying servers. We also noticed that collocating the agents with the core network inside the same servers could be a significant performance boost.

The setup for the End-to-End test where selected based on the Performance results from the LoadCore tests to provide the best possible environment for a UE test. Using the Open5GS reference setup also for the RAN e2e test was not possible because of some MOCN configuration incompatibilities between the used RAN and the Open5GS AMF. All results shown in the end-to-end measurements indicate both good performance and parity with the LoadCore results measured previously. The only discrepancy is the low average R value when compared to the average MOS value.

5 MALAGA MEASUREMENT TOPOLOGIES AND RESULTS

5.1 SYSTEM/SOFTWARE LEVEL MEASUREMENTS

The 6G SANDBOX Malaga platform developments are documented in detail in D4.1 [3] and presented in the project's website⁵. For performance testing, the Malaga platform provides three different configurations, all of them hosted at UMA campus. The reference one is based on Open5GS. The second one uses a combination of Open5GS for the Data plane and an own development of an P4-based UPF. The third setup makes use of the commercial Polaris Unicorn 5G core. In all three configurations, the LoadCore Middleware (MDW) is deployed in a separate server, while the distribution of agents is changing, specifically:

- Reference Trial Network, Open5GS: In this configuration, which is the reference one, both Open5GS and LoadCore agents are deployed at the same server and connected through virtual switches.
- UPF P4 Core Trial Network: In this setup, both Open5GS CP and LoadCore agents are deployed at the same server. However, the Open5GS UP is deactivated and is replaced by the UPF-P4 application, running on an Intel Tofino 2 Switch. The UP connectivity between the agents and UPF is based on high performance physical connections.
- Polaris Trial Network: This third configuration is based on Polaris Unicorn 5G core. All LoadCore agents are deployed in the same server, while Polaris 5GC is installed in a separate one. The connectivity is done physically through a 10 Gb SFP+ switch.

The datasets related to the tests performed for these configurations as described in the sections below are published in ZENODO, as detailed in ANNEX 4 – Malaga Detailed Results.

5.1.1 REFERENCE TRIAL NETWORK

The diagram included in Figure 42 represents the reference setup in Malaga platform. It includes two separate servers: one including Open5GS and LoadCore agents and another with the LoadCore MDW. In both servers, resources are separated in virtual machines under ESXi hypervisor.

Figure 42: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Reference Trial Network in Malaga platform

⁵ <https://6g-sandbox.eu/pilot-6g-sites/malaga/>

In the first server, a complete instantiation of Open5GS including User Plan (UP) and Control Plane (CP) is installed in a single VM. This VM is equipped with 4 CPUs and 4GB of RAM. On the other hand, two additional VMs, each one for a LoadCore agent, are equipped with 2 CPUs and 8 GB of RAM. These two LoadCore agents are used for Data Network and RAN, respectively.

Finally, LoadCore MDW is installed in the second server. Specifically, in a virtual machine with 2 CPUs and 4GB of RAM. The interconnection between the two servers is done through a 10Gb SFP+ Netgear switch. It is important to note that this connection does not affect the performance of the different tests, as the data flow is only occurring on server one, between Open5GS and the LoadCore agents.

1.1.1.16 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

5.1.1.1.1 TEST CASE 1.1: PEAK DATA RATE(PDR)

Table 36: PDR Results for Malaga Platform -Reference TN

DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
2453,52	2298,5	1678,02	1563,28

5.1.1.1.2 TEST CASE 1.2: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PACKET LOSS RATE(PLR)

Table 37: UEDR, PLR Results for Malaga Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	DL UEDR (Mbps)	DL Peak (Mbps)	DL PLR	UL UEDR (Mbps)	UL Peak (Mbps)	UL PLR
14	35,46	37,44	0,77%	3,42	3,95	9,11%
16	31,06	32,5	1,23%	2,98	3,42	9,76%
18	27,62	28,64	1,66%	2,63	3,1	10,31%
20	24,84	25,94	1,99%	2,36	2,78	10,73%

5.1.1.1.3 TEST CASE 2: USER PLANE LATENCY(UPL), DELAY DEVIATION(DD)

Table 38: UPL, DD Results for Malaga Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	DL Average UPL (ms)	UL Average UPL (ms)	DL Average DD (ms)	UL Average DD (ms)
14	0,20	0,14	0,09	0,07
16	0,22	0,15	0,11	0,07
18	0,20	0,18	0,12	0,08
20	0,22	0,14	0,12	0,08

Considering the distribution of the UPL values observed, Figure 43 and Figure 44 depict the UPL value ranges for Uplink and Downlink, and Figure 45, Figure 46 respectively for DD values distribution, during the test case execution involving the maximum number of UEs (20 UEs). Analytical data, for the respective distributions of the executions with 14, 16, 18 and 20 UEs, including the exact number of samples collected per value range can be found in the ANNEX 4 – Malaga Detailed Results.

Figure 43: Downlink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform-Reference TN

Figure 44: Uplink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform-Reference TN

Figure 45: Downlink DD Distribution for Malaga platform-Reference TN

Figure 46: Uplink DD Distribution for Malaga platform-Reference TN

5.1.1.1.4 TEST CASE 3: CONTROL PLANE LATENCY(CPL)

Table 39: CPL Results for Malaga Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	Average CPL (ms)
14	227,6
16	259,2
18	285,2
20	318,2

5.1.1.1.5 TEST CASE 4: AVAILABILITY(AVL)

Test Case 4 in Malaga was run for 46 hours without any disruptions or downtime occurring. This can be seen in Figure 47, in two ways: in the first row by noticing that there are no SCTP abortions from the LoadCore agents, and by noticing a constant data flow during the duration of the tests in the subsequent diagrams, nonetheless within a constrained time window, as captured in the dashboard.

Figure 47: Availability Results for Malaga Platform – Reference TN

5.1.2 UPF P4 TRIAL NETWORK

Figure 48 represents the UPF P4 setup in Malaga platform. There is a similarity between this setup and the reference one in the sense that in this new configuration LoadCore Agents and Open5GS CP are also installed in a single server. In addition, the LoadCore MDW is the same as in the previous trial network. Similarly, resources are separated in VMs and the hypervisor is ESXi. The main difference is in the UP. In this case, Open5GS UPF has been deactivated and it has been replaced by an own UPF development based on P4 language. In order to maximize the performance of the solution, it has been integrated in a programable hardware switch Intel Tofino 2.

Regarding resources allocation, the VM containing the Open5GS CP is equipped with 8 CPUs and 16 GB of RAM. In addition, VMs for LoadCore Agents are both equipped with 8 CPUs and 32 GB of RAM. It is important to note that the provisioning of resources in this configuration is higher than in the reference once, since the idea is to make this setup the one with the highest performance, leveraging the capabilities of the Intel Tofino 2 which ports supporting up to 400 Gbps throughput and hop latency on the order of microseconds.

Finally, connectivity is a key element in this configuration. Even though ports in the Intel Tofino 2 supports 400 Gbps, the server containing the LoadCore Agents with RAN and PDN is equipped with ports limited to 25 Gbps. Thus, despite the connection with the Intel Tofino 2 is done directly to avoid additional hops with switches or routers in between, the bottleneck is found in the interfaces for generation of traffic.

Figure 48: Measurement Topology & Setup for the UPF P4 Trial Network in Malaga platform

1.1.1.17 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

Test cases 1 and 4 are not applicable to this configuration due to a compatibility issue between the server's Network Interface Card (NIC) and LoadCore. The specific NIC is not supported by LoadCore for use as IxStack over Raw Sockets. Although agents can still be hosted on the server, their capabilities are restricted to simple tests.

5.1.2.1.1 TEST CASE 2: USER PLANE LATENCY(UPL), DELAY DEVIATION(DD)

Table 40: UPL, DD Results for Malaga Platform - UPF P4 TN

Number of UEs	DL Average UPL (ms)	UL Average UPL (ms)	DL Average DD (ms)	UL Average DD (ms)
14	0,01	0,04	0	0
16	0,02	0,03	0	0
18	0,01	0,05	0	0
20	0,01	0,04	0	0

Considering the distribution of the UPL values observed, Figure 49 and Figure 50 depict the UPL value ranges for Uplink and Downlink, Figure 51 and Figure 52 respectively for DD values distribution, during the test case execution involving the maximum number of UEs (20 UEs). Analytical data, for the respective distributions of the executions with 14, 16, 18 and 20 UEs, including the exact number of samples collected per value range can be found in the ANNEX 4 – Malaga Detailed Results.

Figure 49: Downlink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform-UPF P4 TN

Figure 50: Uplink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform-UPF P4 TN

Figure 51: Downlink DD Distribution for Malaga platform-UPF P4 TN

Figure 52: Uplink DD Distribution for Malaga platform-UPF P4 TN

5.1.2.1.2 TEST CASE 3: CONTROL PLANE LATENCY(CPL)

Table 41: CPL Results for Malaga Platform - UPF P4 TN

Number of UEs	Average CPL (ms)
14	164,1
16	187,8
18	208,6
20	275,5

5.1.3 POLARIS TRIAL NETWORK

Figure 53 represents the diagram of the third setup in Malaga platform. This configuration is based on the 5GC enterprise solution Polaris Unicorn. Three different servers are included: one for LoadCore agents, another for LoadCore MDW, and a third one hosting the Polaris 5GC. Like in previous configurations, the hypervisor is ESXI, which monitors the VMs in which resources have been separated.

In the first server, two VMs, each one for a LoadCore agent, are equipped with 2 CPUs and 8 GB of RAM. These two LoadCore agents are used for Data Network and RAN, respectively. Resources allocated are the same as in the reference configuration.

Regarding the second server, as explained in the previous setups, the LoadCore MDW is the same in all configurations, thus resources have not been modified.

Finally, the third server hosts the Polaris 5GC. It is installed in a single VM equipped with 8 CPUs and 16 GB of RAM. Connectivity between the core and the agents is done through a 10 Gb SFP+ Netgear switch. In addition, all ports in the servers are 10 Gb SFP+. Thus, without considering limitation on computing resources, the maximum throughput is restricted by these interfaces.

Figure 53: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Polaris Trial Network in Malaga platform

1.1.1.18 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

5.1.3.1.1 TEST CASE 1.1: PEAK DATA RATE(PDR)

Table 42: PDR Results for Malaga Platform -Polaris TN

DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
1.906,23	1.049,81	620,44	571,66

5.1.3.1.2 TEST CASE 1.2: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PACKET LOSS RATE(PLR)

Table 43: Results for Malaga Platform -Polaris TN

Number of UEs	DL UEDR (Mbps)	DL Peak (Mbps)	DL PLR	UL UEDR (Mbps)	UL Peak (Mbps)	UL PLR
14	166,49	183,69	0,00%	31,92	40,33	0,00%
16	154,4	184,38	0,00%	29,03	37,49	0,00%
18	144,24	166	0,00%	21,31	32,03	0,00%
20	109,91	150,35	0,00%	21,87	27,23	0,00%

5.1.3.1.3 TEST CASE 2: USER PLANE LATENCY(UPL), DELAY DEVIATION(DD)

Table 44: UPL, DD Results for Malaga Platform -Polaris TN

Number of UEs	DL Average UPL (ms)	UL Average UPL (ms)	DL Average DD (ms)	UL Average DD (ms)
14	0,75	0,63	0,18	0,22
16	0,75	0,65	0,19	0,23
18	0,75	0,65	0,20	0,23
20	0,73	0,63	0,20	0,23

Considering the distribution of the UPL values observed Figure 54, Figure 55 depict the UPL value ranges for Uplink and Downlink, and Figure 56, Figure 57 respectively for DD values distribution, during the test case execution involving the maximum number of UEs (20 UEs). Analytical data, for the respective distributions of the executions with 14, 16, 18 and 20 UEs, including the exact number of samples collected per value range can be found in the ANNEX 4 – Malaga Detailed Results.

Figure 54: Downlink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform-Polaris TN

Figure 55: Uplink UPL Distribution for Malaga platform- Polaris TN

Figure 56: Downlink DD Distribution for Malaga platform- Polaris TN

Figure 57: Uplink DD Distribution for Malaga platform- Polaris TN

5.1.3.1.4 TEST CASE 3: CONTROL PLANE LATENCY(CPL)

Table 45: CPL Results for Malaga Platform -Polaris TN

Number of UEs	Average CPL (ms)
14	233,5
16	264,0
18	293,0
20	292,0

5.2 END-2-END MEASUREMENTS

5.2.1 OPEN5GS TRIAL NETWORK

Malaga platform also accommodates various 5GCs and RAN configurations. The selected configuration for the end-to-end performance measurements is the Open5GS 5GC and Nokia MicroRRH RAN. The diagram in Figure 58 details the network topology and configuration employed on the Malaga platform for these measurements using the Ixchariot tool. This configuration has been designed to use the reference Trial network defined in the

LoadCore tests (Open5GS) and extend it to provide an e2e network with one of the main RAN infrastructures available at UMA.

In this setup, two endpoints (UEs) OnePlus 10 Pro 5G and Crosscall Core Z5, communicate with the Nokia microRRH NR3500 gNB via both uplink and downlink channels. The gNB is connected to the Nokia AirScale BBU, which is not only controlling these microRRH gNBs, but also Nokia picoRRH cells and mmWave deployment, also available in Malaga. The BBU processes signals from the gNB and interfaces with the Open5GS core network, which is hosted on a VM on Dell PowerEdge R750 XS server provisioned with 4 CPUs and 4GB RAM, running on ESXi infrastructure. The Ixchariot server is hosted as a VM on a Dell PowerEdge R750 server and initiates the performance test by generating synthetic traffic towards the UE, which acts as the endpoint. The IxChariot APK file was deemed necessary to be installed on the UE to utilize IxChariot's network performance testing capabilities directly on the device.

Figure 58: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Open5GS Trial Network in Malaga platform

The configurations for the radio are presented in Table 46 below:

Table 46: Malaga Platform Radio Configuration for End-to-End Measurements

Band	n78 (3500MHz-3600MHz)
Mode	SA
Bandwidth	100 MHz
Carrier-Components	1 carrier
MIMO-layer	4x4
DL MIMO Mode	4x4 Close Loop Spatial Multiplexing
Subcarrier-spacing	30 kHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	1/4

1.1.1.19 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

5.2.1.1.1 TEST CASE 5: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PEAK DATA RATE(PDR), DELAY DEVIATION(DD), MOS SCORES(MOSS)

Table 47: PDR, UEDR End-to-End Results for Malaga Platform

KPI	Value (Mbps)
PDR	59,53
UEDR	44,85

Figure 59: End-to-End Throughput Measurements for Malaga Platform

Table 48: DD End-to-End Results for Malaga Platform

KPI	Value (ms)
DD - Average	3,99
DD - Max	21
DD - Min	2

Table 49: MOS End-to-End Results for Malaga Platform

KPI	Value
MOS - Average	3,96
MOS - Max	4,15
MOS - Min	2,83
MOS – Average R Value	79,14

5.3 ASSURANCE TESTING

6G-SANDBOX Trial Networks will need to be able to be deployed for extended periods of time and retain their performance throughout the entirety of said period. As such, a subset of the tests performed on the reference configuration were repeated later closer to this reports submission to check the consistency of the results and increase the statistical confidence of the results provided. The results for these assurance tests (reported vs. repeated values) for the Malaga platform are reported below.

Table 50: Assurance Testing Results for Malaga Platform

Results	DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
Reported	2453,52	2298,5	1678,02	1563,28
Repeated	2310,73	2203,59	1659,19	1532,41
Delta	5,82%	4,13%	1,12%	1,97%

5.4 RESULT ANALYSIS

Overall, the results for the different configurations measured on the Malaga platform show promising outcomes. In the reference configuration, the Malaga platform achieved a high PDR in both uplink and downlink directions. Additionally, the UEDR results were consistent, further confirming the good performance in terms of both uplink and downlink. Regarding the PLR, the results were slightly worse than expected, although they remain acceptable. Further investigations are necessary to identify the root cause of this issue but seems to be a scalability problem. The reason for the positive results may be attributed to the hosting infrastructure, as all virtual machines were hosted on the same physical server using the ESXi hypervisor.

In the case of UPF P4 Trial Network, good results are obtained for UPL, DD and CPL. However, due to server NIC and LoadCore incompatibility, test cases 1 and 4 could not be tested. Since the actual capabilities of the UPF P4 are limited by the traffic generation in the tests performed, the possibility of mitigating the bottleneck will be investigated, as well as an increase of the generated traffic to show the performance of the UPF P4 in its entirety.

The Polaris Trial Network demonstrated the lowest PDR compared to the reference configuration. However, the UEDR showed significantly better performance than the reference configuration. It is important to highlight the limitation in Open5GS, as an increase in the number of User Equipment leads to a substantial rise in the PLR, particularly in the uplink direction. However, in the case of the Polaris configuration, the PLR remains consistently at 0% in both downlink and uplink, indicating greater stability while increasing number of UEs. This confirms the scalability issue with Open5GS, which is a limitation of the software itself and beyond our ability to address. Furthermore, it is notable that Uplink Latency consistently perform worse on Polaris. In summary, these limitations are more related to the specific software solutions rather than the hardware configurations hosting them.

Finally, the end-to-end results in Malaga show good values for the **Delay Deviation** and **MOS**, but values for **PDR/UEDR** that are significantly lower than expected. These would need to be investigated further, but considering the high performance seen in this aspect for the LoadCore test, it could be due to limitations in the RAN.

6 OULU MEASUREMENT TOPOLOGIES AND RESULTS

6.1 SYSTEM/SOFTWARE LEVEL MEASUREMENTS

The 6G SANDBOX Oulu platform infrastructure is documented in D4.1[3] and presented in the project's website⁶. The University of Oulu platform at this phase provides one trial network configuration hosted as part of the 5G Test Network (5GTN). The configuration is integrated into the 5GTN that offers for example the IP network functionality and internet connection to be used in the reference configuration. Current reference platform is based on Open5GS core and has the necessary server HW and SW to support virtualized environment with necessary virtual machines for both the Open5GS and LoadCore installation. At later phase Oulu Platform will make also other configurations available.

The datasets related to the tests performed for these configurations as described in the sections below are published in ZENODO, as detailed in ANNEX 5 – Oulu Detailed Results.

6.1.1 REFERENCE TRIAL NETWORK

Oulu reference platform is presented in Figure 60. The platform has two servers: Nokia AirFrame has Open5GS installed and the server, Nokia OpenEdge, has LoadCore middleware and the LoadCore Agents installed. Both servers have Ubuntu 24.04 LTS and virtualization environment is created using libvirt and KVM. Open5GS, including Control Plane and User Plane functions, is installed in one VM in the AirFrame server. This VM has 8 CPU's and 8GB RAM available for it. In the other server (Nokia OpenEdge) one VM has the LoadCore middleware installation. This VM has 8 CPU's and 24 GB of RAM. Additionally, there are two VM's where LoadCore Agents are reinstalled. Both virtual machines have 4 CPU's and 8 GB of RAM. IP network connectivity is implemented using 3 switches: Nokia OpenEdge server is connected to Dell S5232F with 100 Gbps connection. Dell S5232F is connected to Juniper QFX5120 also with 100 Gbps link. Next the Juniper QFX5120 is connected to Juniper QFX5100 with 40 Gbps. Finally, the Juniper QFX5100 is connected to the Nokia AirFrame with two 10 Gbps connections.

Figure 60: Measurement Topology & Setup for the Reference Trial Network in Oulu platform

⁶ <https://6g-sandbox.eu/pilot-6g-sites/oulu/>.

1.1.1.20 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

6.1.1.1.1 TEST CASE 1.1: PEAK DATA RATE(PDR)

Table 51: PDR Results for Oulu Platform -Reference TN

DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
1.010,75	977,78	1.062,14	1.016,51

6.1.1.1.2 TEST CASE 1.2: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PACKET LOSS RATE(PLR)

Table 52:UEDR, PLR Results for Oulu Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	DL UEDR (Mbps)	DL Peak (Mbps)	DL PLR	UL UEDR (Mbps)	UL Peak (Mbps)	UL PLR
14	35,24	37,19	1,35%	3,42	3,96	7,26%
16	30,83	32,6	1,95%	2,99	3,49	8,65%
18	27,38	29,06	2,25%	2,66	3,12	8,29%
20	24,65	25,98	2,82%	2,39	2,75	8,64%

6.1.1.1.3 TEST CASE 2: USER PLANE LATENCY(UPL), DELAY DEVIATION(DD)

Table 53: UPL, DD Results for Oulu Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	DL Average UPL (ms)	UL Average UPL (ms)	DL Average DD (ms)	UL Average DD (ms)
14	0,13	0,15	0,03	0,03
16	0,14	0,15	0,03	0,03
18	0,17	0,14	0,03	0,03
20	0,15	0,16	0,03	0,03

Considering the distribution of the UPL values observed, Figure 49 and Figure 50 depict the UPL value ranges for Uplink and Downlink, Figure 51 and Figure 52 respectively for DD values distribution, during the test case execution involving the maximum number of UEs (20 UEs). Analytical data, for the respective distributions of the executions with 14, 16, 18 and 20 UEs, including the exact number of samples collected per value range can be found in the ANNEX 5 – Oulu Detailed Results.

Figure 61: Downlink UPL Distribution for Oulu platform-Reference TN

Figure 62: Uplink UPL Distribution for Oulu platform-Reference TN

Figure 63: Downlink DD Distribution for Oulu platform-Reference TN

Figure 64: Uplink DD Distribution for Oulu platform-Reference TN

6.1.1.1.4 TEST CASE 3: CONTROL PLANE LATENCY(CPL)

Table 54: CPL Results for Oulu Platform -Reference TN

Number of UEs	Average CPL (s)
14	228,3
16	247,6
18	297,1
20	327,2

6.1.1.1.5 TEST CASE 4: AVAILABILITY(AVL)

Test Case 4 in Oulu was run for 90 hours without any disruptions or downtime occurring. This can be seen in Figure 65, in two ways: in the first row by noticing that there are no SCTP abortions from the LoadCore agents, and by noticing a constant data flow during the duration of the tests in the subsequent diagrams, nonetheless within a constrained time window, as captured in the dashboard.

Figure 65: Availability Measurements for Oulu Platform – Reference TN

6.2 END-2-END MEASUREMENTS

6.2.1 END-TO-END NETWORK

The University of Oulu platform for the End-To-End measurements utilizes the same basic architecture that was used for the LoadCore tests. The architecture is presented Figure 66. Two more virtual machines were created to the same Nokia Airframe server where the Open5GS already exists in its own VM. Utilizing the same Server for ixChariot as for the Open5GS it possible to minimize the data transmission related delays in the system between these two instances. Both new VM's have 8 CPU's and 8 GB of RAM. Open5GS core is then connected through 2 Juniper switches to Nokia Baseband unit AMIA that has ABIL and ASIB modules installed. Baseband unit is connected through Nokia ASiR HUB to Nokia AWHQA 5G radio. There are two Mobile Phone Endpoints connected to the AWHQA in SA mode. Both UE's are Nokia model XR21.

Figure 66: OULU measurement topology for End-To-End tests

Table 55 lists the Oulu platform radio and channel related parameters.

Table 55: Oulu Platform Radio Configuration for End-to-End Measurements

Band	n78, center frq 3540 MHz
Mode	TDD
Bandwidth	60 MHz
Carrier-Components	1 carrier
MIMO-layer	4T2R
DL MIMO Mode	4x4
Subcarrier-spacing	30 kHz
Uplink/Downlink slot ratio	4:1 DDDSU

1.1.1.21 BENCHMARKING RESULTS

6.2.1.1.1 TEST CASE 5: USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR), PEAK DATA RATE(PDR), DELAY DEVIATION(DD), MOS SCORES(MOSS)

Table 56: PDR, UEDR DD End-to-End Results for Oulu Platform

KPI	Value (Mbps)
PDR	518,01
UEDR	356,01

Figure 67: End to End throughput measurements for the Oulu Platform

Table 57: DD End-to-End Results for Oulu Platform

KPI	Value (ms)
DD - Average	3,63
DD - Max	7
DD - Min	1

Table 58: MOS End-to-End Results for Oulu Platform

KPI	Value
MOS - Average	4,04
MOS - Max	4,15
MOS - Min	3,20
MOS – Average R Value	81,02

6.3 ASSURANCE TESTING

6G-SANDBOX Trial Networks will need to be able to be deployed for extended periods of time and retain their performance throughout the entirety of said period. As such, a subset of the tests performed throughout this report were repeated later closer to this reports submission to check the consistency of the results and increase the statistical confidence of the results provided. The results for these assurance tests (reported vs. repeated values) for the Oulu platform are reported below.

Table 59: Assurance Testing Results for Oulu Platform

Results	DL PDR (Mbps)	DL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)	UL PDR (Mbps)	UL 95 th Percentile (Mbps)
Reported	1.010,75	977,78	1.062,14	1.016,51
Repeated	845,43	828,42	834,88	780,85
Delta	16,36%	15,27%	21,39%	23,18%

6.4 RESULT ANALYSIS

There was only one test platform deployed in OULU. Two more with different architectures are to be added during 2H/2024. Therefore, the OULU test results are for the same Open5GS based platform.

In test case 1.1: Peak Data Rate, the platform is performing well as all the results are around 1000 Mbps. OULU is therefore in the middle of all of the measurement results when comparing with other platforms. In test case 1.2: User Experienced Data Rate, Packet Loss Rate OULU platform is again performing well and especially the uplink packet loss rate figures are low. On the other hand, there is room for some improvement in the downlink direction and we will be looking into it to find ways to improve it. Test case 2: User Plane Latency, Delay Deviation is showing very good performance for Oulu platform. Actually, the performance for example in DL average UPL is at worst only 0.17 ms and in UL average UPL even less showing very low latency figures for the platform. Also, the delay deviation 0.03 ms indicates really good performance. The uplink and downlink delay distributions are also showing good performance of the network as only 2% of the measured downlink latency is over 0.25 ms. For uplink the same figure is even better when 100% of the latencies are below 0.25 ms. There is almost no delay deviation in the measurement results as 98% of the DL and 99% of the results are in the lowest result category. Test case 3: Control Plane Latency shows the same kind of results as almost all of the platforms. In Test case 4: Availability OULU platform ran for 90 hours without disruptions or downtime. In Test case 5: User Experienced Data Rate, Peak Data Rate, Delay Deviation, MOS Scores OULU platform is performing as expected and the performance results are on good level.

In the Assurance testing there is a clear 15 to 23 percent degradation in the repeated measurements results compared to the reported results. There is obviously reason to find out the root cause for it. We will focus on that as a priority task during Q3/2024.

7 RESULT ANALYSIS AND COMPARISON

The canvas for the project-wide results analysis is the reference trial network topology, and the baseline system/software level measurements, as these setups have a common basis in respect to the compute resources dimensioning per platform.

7.1 INTER PLATFORM RESULTS

The common across platforms Reference Trial Network deployment allows room for inter-platform comparison results, considering that fundamental parameters such as core network software and resources were commonly agreed. Actual testbeds configurations for the reference scenario are as follows.

Table 60: 5G Core System Specifications per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)

	LoadCore Agent (UE)	LoadCore Agent (DN)	Open5gs core		
			Control Plane Functions	User Plane Functions	Host Server
Athens	CPU: 4 cores RAM: 8GB	CPU: 4 cores RAM: 8GB	1 VM, NFs running as containers. CPU: 2 cores RAM: 8GB	1 VM with UPF running as container. CPU: 4 cores RAM: 8GB	All VMs on kvm hypervisor in one host with 4CPUs and 132GB RAM and processor model: Intel(R) Xeon(R) E-2314 CPU @2.80GHz
Berlin	vCPU: 4 RAM: 8 GB	vCPU: 4 RAM: 8 GB	CP & UP in one VM vCPU: 4 RAM: 4GB		OpenNebula(kvm) hypervisor scheduled on different servers each equipped with 4 CPU's and 128 to 256 GB of RAM and processor model: Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2680 v4 @ 2.40GHz or Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2640 0 @ 2.50GHz or Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2630 v3 @ 2.40GHz and.
Malaga	vCPU: 2 RAN: 8GB	vCPU: 2 RAN: 8GB	CP & UP in one VM vCPU: 4 RAM: 4GB		All VMs on ESXI hypervisor in one host with 64 CPUs and 192 GB RAM and processor model: Intel Xeon gold 6326 CPU @2.90 GHz
Oulu	VCPU: 4 RAM: 8 GB	VCPU: 4 RAM: 8 GB	CP & UP in one VM VCPU: 8 RAM: 8 GB		Ubuntu 24.04 + libvirt + KVM Nokia AirFrame: 2*14 Core Intel XEON E5-2680 v4 128 GB DDR ECC RAM 2*447 GB nvme ssd

Overall, the results for the reference configuration at the system/software level show a decent amount of parity between the platforms. While having a 0% delta is unrealistic, the achieved deltas prove that the reference configuration concept can be used to achieve a baseline level of inter-platform calibration and to ensure that any prospective 6G-SANDBOX platform can provide definable basic characteristics. The road taken to reach this level of parity was significant, however. All platforms went through multiple iterations of their reference configurations, as more and more performance compromising factors were identified that were not predicted before the deployment. A significant amount of these factors were to do with the virtualization methods and parameters. The significance of the effect on performance of these factors was unexpected and lead to conclusions about the definition of reference configurations in the future, which are further detailed in Section 8. Hardware was also seen to have a noticeable effect on performance, specifically infrastructure components which could act as performance bottlenecks despite the high-performance servers they were connecting. These

factors were and, in some cases, still are in the process of being identified and rectified to achieve the highest possible level of parity between the reference configurations and to inform future testing and calibration within 6G-SANDBOX.

For the purposes of actual comparison, for each KPI, one platform is chosen to be the baseline. This choice is made based on which platform had the overall best performance for the given KPI. The reason for this is that as a testing infrastructure being designed for 6G, any reference should be the best possible result at any time. For each KPI, the results for each platform are shown, as well as the deltas for each platform compared to the baseline platform. In the cases where for a single result one of the platforms performs better than the baseline, this will be demarcated in **green**. The baseline results are demarcated with the word **BASE**.

7.1.1 AGGREGATED RESULTS PER KPI

1.1.1.22 PEAK DATA RATE(PDR)

PDR is perhaps the simplest and most efficient way to gauge the throughput performance of each of the platforms at a glance.

Table 61: Peak Data Rate Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)

Peak Data Rate Per Platform (Mbps)				
	Athens	Berlin	Malaga	Oulu
Uplink	322,87	1297,36	1678,02	1062,14
Downlink	528,14	1039,01	2453,52	1010,75
Delta from Malaga to other platforms in terms of Peak Data Rate				
	Uplink Delta	Downlink Delta	Average Delta	
Athens	80,76%	78,47%	79,62%	
Berlin	22,69%	57,65%	40,17%	
Malaga	BASE	BASE	BASE	
Oulu	36,70%	58,80%	47,75%	

The Malaga platform was able to achieve the highest **PDR** here in both uplink and downlink and is therefore selected as the baseline. All three other platforms achieved notably lower **PDR** values, with Athens having a significantly large delta, 79,62% on average.

1.1.1.23 USER EXPERIENCED DATA RATE(UEDR)

UEDR allows for the operating floor in terms of throughput for each platform to be characterized, showing what throughput values are expected 95% of the time when operating the trial network.

Table 62: Average User Experienced Data Rate Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)

Average User Experienced Data Rate Per Platform (Mbps)				
	Athens	Berlin	Malaga	Oulu
14UE Uplink	3,39	3,42	3,42	3,42
14UE Downlink	21,42	35,22	35,46	35,24
16UE Uplink	2,96	2,98	2,98	2,99
16UE Downlink	19,39	30,84	31,06	30,83
18UE Uplink	2,62	2,65	2,63	2,66
18UE Downlink	15,94	27,4	27,62	27,38
20UE Uplink	2,35	2,38	2,36	2,39
20UE Downlink	14,02	24,68	24,84	24,65

Table 63: Delta Measurements of Average User Experienced Data Rate Measurements from the base platform (Malaga)

Delta from Malaga to other platforms in terms of User Experienced Data Rate										
	14UE UL Delta	14UE DL Delta	16UE UL Delta	16UE DL Delta	18UE UL Delta	18UE DL Delta	20UE UL Delta	20UE DL Delta	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	0,88%	39,59%	0,67%	37,57	0,38%	42,29%	0,42%	43,56%	0,59%	40,75%
Berlin	0%	0,68%	0%	0,71%	0,76%	0,80%	0,85%	0,64%	0,40%	0,71%
Malaga	BASE	BASE								
Oulu	0%	0,62%	0,34%	0,74%	1,14%	0,87%	1,27%	0,76%	0,69%	0,75%

A consensus is more difficult to reach here than with the previous set of results. While both Oulu and Berlin show better performance than Malaga in terms of uplink on average, Malaga is still selected as the baseline due to the consistency of its results when looking at both uplink and downlink. In general, there is a sub 1% difference between the results of all three platforms. While the downlink deltas for Athens do stand out, the overall lower delta values for **UEDR** indicate that the platforms have greater parity when it comes to baseline user experience.

1.1.1.24 PACKET LOSS RATE (PLR)

The **PLR** allows for the characterization of the consistency of traffic flow, and when combined with throughput based KPIs gives a better picture of the nature of traffic flow in the network.

Table 64: Packet Loss Rate Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)

Packet Loss Rate Per Platform (%)				
	Athens	Berlin	Malaga	Oulu
14UE Uplink	8,36	8,38	9,11	7,26
14UE Downlink	0,56	0,82	0,77	1,35
16UE Uplink	8,99	9,11	9,76	8,65
16UE Downlink	0,82	1,26	1,23	1,95
18UE Uplink	9,73	9,03	10,31	8,29
18UE Downlink	1,08	1,64	1,66	2,25
20UE Uplink	10,31	9,56	10,73	8,64
20UE Downlink	1,34	1,97	1,99	2,82

Table 65: Delta Measurements of Packet Loss Rate Measurements from the base platform (Athens)

Delta from Athens to other platforms in terms of the Packet Loss Rate										
	14UE UL Delta	14UE DL Delta	16UE UL Delta	16UE DL Delta	18UE UL Delta	18UE DL Delta	20UE UL Delta	20UE DL Delta	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	BASE	BASE								
Berlin	0,24%	46,43 %	1,33 %	53,66%	7,19%	51,85%	7,27 %	47,01%	3,42%	49,74%
Malaga	8,97%	37,50 %	8,57 %	50,00%	5,96%	53,70%	4,07 %	48,51%	6,89%	47,43%
Oulu	13,16%	141,0 7%	3,78 %	137,80 %	14,80 %	108,33 %	16,2 %	110,45 %	11,99%	124,41%

A clear baseline is a little less clear cut in the **PLR** results. In this case, Athens is chosen due to having the best all-round performance. Oulu and Berlin have better **PLR** values for uplink, but lag Athens significantly in downlink. In general, all the platforms show similar uplink performance, while in downlink Athens puts forward the best results by a significant margin.

1.1.1.25 USER PLANE LATENCY (UPL)

The **UPL** characterizes the latency in the network experienced by the user.

Table 66: Average User Plane Latency Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)

	Average User Plane Latency Per Platform (ms)			
	Athens	Berlin	Malaga	Oulu
14UE Uplink	8,09	0,19	0,14	0,15
14UE Downlink	27,03	0,47	0,20	0,13
16UE Uplink	8,43	0,19	0,15	0,15
16UE Downlink	27,04	0,45	0,22	0,14
18UE Uplink	8,47	0,18	0,18	0,14
18UE Downlink	26,81	0,46	0,20	0,17
20UE Uplink	8,47	0,21	0,14	0,16
20UE Downlink	27,15	0,45	0,22	0,15

Table 67: Delta Measurements of Packet Loss Rate Measurements from the base platform (Oulu)

	Delta from Oulu to other platforms in terms of Average User Plane Latency									
	14UE UL Delta	14UE DL Delta	16UE UL Delta	16UE DL Delta	18UE UL Delta	18UE DL Delta	20UE UL Delta	20UE DL Delta	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	5293,3 3%	20.692, 31%	5520,0 0%	19.214, 89%	5950,0 0%	15.670, 59%	5193,7 5%	18.000, 00%	5.489, 27%	18.394, 45%
Berlin	26,67 %	261,54 %	26,67 %	221,43 %	28,57 %	170,59 %	31,25 %	200% %	28,29% %	213,39 %
Malaga	6,67% %	53,85% %	0% %	57,14% %	28,57 %	17,65% %	12,50 %	46,67% %	9,4% %	43,83% %
Oulu	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE

Malaga and Oulu seem to have similar latency values here, with Oulu having the lowest values overall and acting as the baseline. Both Athens and Berlin experience notably higher latency values, with Athens platform appearing to experience higher latency attributed to the containerized Open5GS installation (not the case for the rest platforms) as well as the overhead of the virtualization manager used.

1.1.1.26 DELAY DEVIATION (DD)

The **DD** characterizes the consistency of the **UPL**, showing how much variation there is in the experienced latency.

Table 68: Average Delay Deviation Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)

	Average Delay Deviation Per Platform(ms)			
	Athens	Berlin	Malaga	Oulu
14UE Uplink	2,63	0,07	0,07	0,03
14UE Downlink	1,07	0,11	0,09	0,03
16UE Uplink	2,93	0,06	0,07	0,03
16UE Downlink	1,20	0,07	0,11	0,03
18UE Uplink	3,12	0,06	0,08	0,03
18UE Downlink	1,30	0,06	0,12	0,03
20UE Uplink	3,38	0,08	0,08	0,03
20UE Downlink	1,43	0,10	0,12	0,03

Table 69: Delta Measurements of Delay Deviation Measurements from the base platform (Oulu)

	Delta from Oulu to other platforms in terms of Delay Deviation									
	14UE UL Delta	14UE DL Delta	16UE UL Delta	16UE DL Delta	18UE UL Delta	18UE DL Delta	20UE UL Delta	20UE DL Delta	Average Uplink Delta	Average Downlink Delta
Athens	8666,67%	3466,67%	9666,67%	3900,00%	10.300,00%	4233,33%	11.166,67%	4666,67%	9950,00%	4066,67%
Berlin	133,33%	266,67%	100,00%	133,33%	100,00%	100,00%	166,67%	233,33%	125,00%	183,33%
Malaga	133,33%	200,00%	133,33%	266,67%	166,67%	300,00%	166,67%	300,00%	150,00%	266,67%
Oulu	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE

Oulu shows the lowest **DD** values, which means it is set as the baseline. This matches its good performance in terms of **UPL**. All three other platforms show notably large deltas in this case.

1.1.1.27 CONTROL PLANE LATENCY(CPL)

The **CPL** characterizes the responsiveness of the control plane, showing how much time it takes for it to change the states of UEs.

Table 70:: Average Control Plane Latency Measurements per 6G SANDBOX Platform (Reference TN)

	Average Control Plane Latency Per Platform(ms)			
	Athens	Berlin	Malaga	Oulu
14UE	249,4	221,2	227,6	228,3
16UE	291,2	247,1	259,2	274,6
18UE	324,3	275,6	285,2	297,1
20UE	372,8	314,6	318,2	327,2

Table 71: Delta Measurements of Control Plane Latency Measurements from the base platform (Berlin)

	Delta from Berlin to other platforms in terms of Control Plane Latency				
	14UE Delta	16UE Delta	18UE Delta	20UE Delta	Average Delta
Athens	12,75%	17,85%	17,67%	18,50%	16,69%
Berlin	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE	BASE
Malaga	2,89%	4,90%	3,48%	1,14%	3,10%
Oulu	3,21%	11,13%	7,80%	4,00%	6,54%

Berlin was selected as a baseline due to having the lowest **CPL** values. The results from the other platforms do not have significant deltas however, and overall, the **CPL** performance appears to be quite consistent.

7.2 INTRA PLATFORM RESULTS

In this section, the results of the non-reference configurations for each of the platforms will be compared to their reference configuration to identify general trends and notable deltas. Due to the significant differences between the configurations, the analysis will not be as in depth as Section 7.1, staying on a more surface level. The main analysis to be taken from these testing efforts is the assurance that 6G-SANDBOX can create and test a large variety of trial networks even at this early stage of implementation. In the future, given more granularity in the differences between the configurations, this method will be used to perform Intra-Platform Calibration, as discussed in Section 2.

7.2.1 ATHENS

The second deployment of the system/software level configuration in Athens, utilizing ATHONET 5G core network, shows significant improvements over the reference trial network deployment with Open5GS. This is evident in practically every single KPI, but especially noticeable in the **Packet Loss Rate** where it drops down to practically 0%. Latency performance is also significantly improved, with both **User Plane Latency** and **Delay Deviation** dropping down to more expected values. **Peak Data Rate** reaches just below 1000Mbps for both uplink and downlink, an improvement of 400% and 200% respectively.

The third deployment in Athens is an alternate version of the reference, with the location of the LoadCore agents changed to be at their second physical location. As can be expected, results here are fairly similar to the Reference configuration. The **User Experienced Data Rate** sees a notable increase, however, so does the **User Plane Latency**. This can perhaps be expected due to the increase in distance between network components.

7.2.2 BERLIN

Berlin's second configuration, the ESX Open5GCore, shows results that range from similar to significantly improved compared to the reference trial network deployment. While the **User Experienced Data Rate** is practically identical, the **Peak Data Rate** increases significantly, to over 2Gbps for both uplink and downlink. **Packet Loss Rate** and **User Plane Latency** both also see marked improvements, as does **Control Plane Latency**.

Berlin's third configuration also used their Open5GCore, but instead ran it through OpenNebula. Both **Peak Data Rate** and **User Experienced Data Rate** showed very similar results to the reference configuration. **User Plane Latency** was also similar, although the uplink latency was slower than the reference. The **Control Plane Latency** was a little worse than the reference implementation, especially at the higher UE counts.

7.2.3 MALAGA

Malaga's UPF P4 was only able to run Test Case 2 due to hardware restrictions but showed off its high performance by achieving **User Plane Latency** and **Delay Deviation** results that were 10 times better than those achieved by the reference configuration. The **Delay Deviation** results are particularly impressive here, being consistently sub 5us. Significant improvement can be seen in the **Control Plane Latency** as well.

The performance of the Polaris configuration was a little more mixed. Throughput in general was improved in comparison to the reference, but the **User Plane Latency** and **Delay Deviation** were noticeably worse. Interestingly, the **Control Plane Latency** was also improved, implying that the latency issues are user plane specific.

8 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable constitutes an interim report on testing efforts within 6G-SANDBOX, and as such the conclusions drawn serve to inform the direction and methodology of testing undertaken as the project continues forward. There are three main areas that the work behind this report has informed and the conclusions in these areas will be discussed in this section.

Although not documented in this report, a significant amount of time was expended in the process of preparing testing solutions, mating platforms to measurement infrastructure and defining the necessary parameters for said infrastructure to be able to run tests and collect measurements. While expected to some extent due to comparative low level of maturity in the platforms at the start of the testing process, this does have some ramifications about future developments within 6G-SANDBOX. As mentioned previously, while all the testing process documented in this report was done by hand, one of the goals of 6G-SANDBOX is for the entirety of the testing process to be as automated as possible. This includes the setting up of necessary tools that an experimenter may require to perform their desired tests. Considering the level of difficulty experienced in this task during this initial testing phase, it raises some questions about the possibility of automating this task. This was especially evident when using the LoadCore tool. While IxChariot performs 'black box' measurements and doesn't need to know details about the network that its measuring, LoadCore interconnects with network elements intricately and often each deployment has some level of uniqueness due to differences in the network/core architecture. This complexity and specificity mean that automating this process would either take a significant amount of time and/or be an ongoing task as new potential trial networks are added or would require an extremely complex automation algorithm to implement correctly. At time of writing work is beginning on automating the test cases detailed in this report, but automation of testing environment setup is still some ways off. When the time comes to begin developing this automation, decisions will need to be made about the capabilities and level of complexity that automation will take in this specific area.

A large part of the work was focused on developing and implementing ideas of Inter and Intra Platform Calibration. The development of these ideas has had a huge impact on testing methodology within 6G-SANDBOX, as it will allow any results measured in 6G-SANDBOX to be put into context, making sure experimenters fully understand the performance implications of any new components they introduce into the network. Over the course of the implementation of these calibration methods described in this report, interesting discoveries have already been made. While it is unrealistic to expect identical results from each of the platforms, some of the initial collected results from the Reference Configurations had deltas that ranged in the multiple orders of magnitude. This led to a process of multiple platforms investigating both the details of their setups and how those details differed from the setups at other platforms. The largest effect in reducing these deltas was achieved when the methods and parameters relating to virtualization were changed. This includes hypervisor settings, VM configuration differences, hardware differences and VM placement among other things. The scale of this effect was surprising, as it was not expected that these factors would have such a significant impact on the performance, and as such they were not included in the process of the definition of the Reference configuration. This is something that will need to change in the future, as it is clear that the granularity of the Reference Trial Network definition needs to be increased for it to serve its intended purpose.

A key initiative spinning-off from these observations, has been to standardize the 'Reference Trial Network (TN)' as a system set-up that can be automatically deployed from the 6G SANDBOX life cycle manager component (TNLCM), specifying not only the computational capacity assumed, but incorporating technical specifications such as the optimized virtualization platform (OpenNebula) verified by the project, and the recommended technical parameters affecting the compute (e.g. provisioning) and networking (e.g. VLAN or XVLAN) operation. Such a standardized 'Reference Trial Network' can serve as the basis for experimenters to calibrate their experiment results, and through the 6G SANDBOX experimentation automation leverage repeatable, reliable, and transparent performance results. The result of this activity is the formulation of an analytic trial network

template for generating descriptors, published under a dedicated TN library in the project's github⁷. Going forward for testing in 6G-SANDBOX, these descriptors will be considered to enhance both Inter and Intra platform calibration methods and provide a better understanding of the platforms' performance and deltas.

While this report details the technical efforts undertaken in the initial steps of testing implementation for 6G-SANDBOX, the most important conclusions taken from the entire venture is the development of the testing methodologies and the ideas and inter and intra platform calibration techniques. With these methods defined, 6G-SANDBOX now has the capability not only to run tests and present results, but also to present the impact on any changes in a trial network in terms of performance deltas. This is helpful for both the experimenter and platform operator. For the experimenter, it allows them to have a greater understanding of the performance impact of their component under test by ensuring they not only know its characteristics but how it changes the characteristics of the network it is deployed in. For platform operators, it allows them to iterate on their platform designs intelligently, understanding the relative impact of any changes they make giving them a more in-depth understanding of their capabilities. These methods will be vital for the testing process moving forward within 6G-SANDBOX.

9 REFERENCES

- [1] 6G-SANDBOX, "D2.1 Ecosystem Analysis and 6G-SANDBOX Facility design," 6G-SANDBOX, 2023, https://6g-sandbox.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/6G-SANDBOX_D2.1_v1.5.pdf
- [2] 6G-SANDBOX, "D5.1 Definition of evaluation approach and test system", 6G-SANDBOX, 2024, https://6g-sandbox.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/D5.1_6G-SANDBOX-v1.pdf
- [3] 6G-SANDBOX, "D4.1 Integration and Management for 6G trial networks – Intermediate report", 6G-SANDBOX, 2024, https://6g-sandbox.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/6G-SANDBOX_D4.1_v1.0.pdf
- [4] 6G SANDBOX, "D3.1 6G-SANDBOX Library V1", <https://6g-sandbox.eu/dissemination/deliverables/>

⁷: https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/TNLCM/blob/main/descriptors/reference_tn.yaml

ANNEX 1 – TCP THROUGHPUT LOG EXTRACTION AND ANALYSIS

When a test running TCP traffic is complete, csv files containing the uplink and the downlink throughput data/logs are downloaded from the LoadCore Middleware. The throughput data is extracted from these csv files and placed into the corresponding sheet in a results spreadsheet, sorted in ascending order. Next, an Empirical Density Function (EDF) is created. This is done by filling the cell next to the smallest throughput result with a zero, and then making the cell below it equal to the following formula:

$$EDF_{VAL} = PrevCell + \frac{1}{Number\ of\ datapoints}$$

This equation is repeated for all further datapoints, such that each data point by the end has a corresponding EDF value. These EDF values can be used to find percentiles. For example, the 20th percentile throughput value is the first data point with an EDF value of 0.2 or higher.

When running a test using TCP traffic, some settings are set generically, no matter the purpose of the test. These are listed here:

Setting Name	Value
TCP Send Buffer	65535
TCP Receive Buffer	65535

ANNEX 2 – ATHENS DETAILED RESULTS

6G-SANDBOX (2024). Data set from the 6G-SANDBOX platforms benchmarking and assessment for different documented trial networks - Athens facility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373419>

REFERENCE TRIAL NETWORK

Downlink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	7.411	42.979	199.361	406.236	2.029.109	4.568.161	11.656.387	14.722.594	38.391.307
16	3.879	37.619	185.984	393.807	2.035.796	4.688.269	11.649.317	14.653.283	38.233.235
18	12.174	51.883	219.700	426.037	2.031.998	4.777.241	12.017.900	14.832.480	38.256.778
20	8.335	43.688	193.334	394.370	2.025.733	4.539.615	11.511.906	14.737.979	38.489.414

Uplink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	14.157	84.990	343.311	895.635	5.915.939	4.136.711	2.107.667	1.212.317	1.235.010
16	15.710	83.183	321.459	832.683	5.697.984	4.204.471	2.199.951	1.264.893	1.346.658
18	8.595	62.363	297.422	831.408	5.703.429	4.216.560	2.200.742	1.266.829	1.369.083
20	10.792	58.876	262.060	750.285	5.561.429	4.232.711	2.255.035	1.324.577	1.465.923

Downlink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	21.789.815	12.270.268	12.810.496	9.062.351	12.572.418	2.396.280	680.770	250.096	191.051
16	18.797.695	12.323.378	12.704.334	9.900.363	14.129.155	3.734.069	989.565	284.330	218.300
18	16.375.532	13.146.929	12.806.429	10.490.325	15.254.424	3.098.489	886.131	324.855	243.077
20	13.383.292	13.860.688	12.401.137	11.005.720	16.157.090	3.496.267	994.572	365.538	280.070

Uplink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	2.202.589	956.359	1.235.629	1.933.715	7.430.047	1.504.622	413.719	151.797	114.260
16	1.836.100	973.099	1.166.440	1.824.241	7.636.674	1.724.798	488.805	176.728	140.107
18	1.613.375	969.086	1.116.909	1.782.458	7.722.848	1.888.138	522.365	191.842	149.410
20	1.391.498	917.481	1.048.345	1.689.472	7.782.347	2.108.010	590.774	219.545	174.216

ENTERPRISE (ATHONET) TRIAL NETWORK

Downlink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	0	1.242.995	122.912.751	36.227.774	296.026	16.127	993	42	0
16	0	640.026	121.771.277	37.910.852	316.248	21.491	1.227	104	7.918
18	0	1.890.009	129.456.232	29.041.539	284.447	20.073	1.603	534	2211
20	0	573.134	123.985.114	35.785.164	327.251	22.192	2.168	98	0

Uplink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	484.492	12.496.810	2.904.541	163.969	18.508	1.906	75	28	117
16	1.514.117	11.308.464	3.072.901	156.832	16.850	1.274	20	5	0
18	895.323	11.338.085	3.664.881	154.590	16.315	1.208	59	3	0
20	623.510	11.861.352	3.317.429	248.141	18.452	1.345	75	29	131

Downlink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	136.989.274	18.067.072	5.563.623	46.250	27.989	2.435	65	0	0
16	109.115.000	49.058.710	2.403.836	50.813	37.128	3.517	75	0	64
18	83.111.767	76.472.440	1.021.104	49.165	38.665	3.385	96	0	36
20	85.359.336	73.981.034	1.248.972	52.149	49.637	3.809	172	12	0

Uplink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	14.840.707	798.949	375.481	27.336	26.619	1.299	35	6	14
16	13.909.432	1.686.627	422.758	26.654	24.002	975	12	3	0
18	13.896.984	1.660.870	461.462	26.653	23.437	995	61	2	0
20	13.743.568	1.720.867	548.677	30.229	25.940	1.097	60	6	20

OPEN5GS/MOCN – DISTRIBUTED AGENTS DEPLOYMENT TRIAL NETWORK

Downlink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	0	3	90.364	750.913	1.406.970	2.035.015	5.241.264	10.962.700	33.107.376
16	0	0	100.278	742.934	1.391.942	2.044.034	5.324.215	10.608.215	33.237.532
18	0	0	69.060	706.485	1.408.728	2.082.814	5.367.375	11.099.605	33.380.599
20	0	0	125.229	907.209	1.481.307	1.995.905	5.237.292	10.512.677	32.713.305

Uplink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	0	0	34.740	1.065.860	5.614.785	3.194.926	1.945.657	1.506.429	2.431.741
16	0	0	28.726	1.039.739	5.595.968	3.143.787	1.935.079	1.508.732	2.535.035
18	0	1	48.427	1.133.724	5.572.449	3.129.404	1.933.327	1.507.129	2.464.925
20	0	0	19.415	765.653	5.283.602	3.233.269	2.040.425	1.595.654	2.815.929

Downlink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	9.447.389	10.063.122	14.583.416	7.397.935	10.562.156	1.117.399	271.277	88.653	63.258
16	8.512.099	8.838.090	15.233.854	7.953.143	11.167.362	1.264.684	308.864	100.542	70.512
18	8.294.730	8.113.853	15.223.925	8.647.261	11.750.399	1.519.177	364.542	119.473	81.306
20	8.101.649	7.308.064	14.111.268	8.941.388	12.078.368	1.773.902	414.128	141.368	102.789

Uplink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	794.973	706.365	1.206.412	1.823.594	9.683.066	920.561	344.237	158.714	156.216
16	755.911	704.092	1.262.888	1.878.710	9.498.854	965.600	387.589	163.751	169.671
18	781.067	754.993	1.214.480	1.832.115	9.407.185	1.014.258	411.290	191.563	182.435
20	8.101.649	7.308.064	14.111.268	8.941.388	12.078.368	1.773.902	414.128	141.368	102.789

ANNEX 3 – BERLIN DETAILED RESULTS

6G-SANDBOX (2024). Data set from the 6G-SANDBOX platforms benchmarking and assessment for different documented trial networks - Berlin facility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373435>

REFERENCE TRIAL NETWORK

Downlink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	491	2.692.099	103.337.418	66.600.850	362.401	39.998	15.543	8.757	8.355
16	1.125	4.673.831	109.097.847	58.999.144	320.074	14.236	1.315	17	0
18	2.145	4.447.677	107.515.915	60.801.078	330.050	16.914	1.113	237	0
20	772	4.473.640	108.850.712	59.402.204	329.204	26.157	1.330	90	0

Uplink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	3.180.474	12.100.489	1.918.463	88.203	14.394	3.620	1.682	867	429
16	2.614.441	12.886.457	1.714.568	78.465	13.705	1.214	34	2	0
18	3.148.903	12.413.504	1.665.499	73.966	15.314	1.572	112	15	0
20	2.311.515	11.470.250	3.359.771	152.562	13.540	1.136	86	5	0

Downlink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	135.073.382	6.194.534	31.620.035	130.096	42.508	4.088	644	330	295
16	148.499.437	8.251.370	16.185.114	121.809	47.261	2.502	96	0	0
18	146.141.777	16.234.826	10.547.169	132.359	56.112	2.757	86	43	0
20	127.849.474	21.348.415	23.659.323	160.679	60.967	5.155	96	0	0

Uplink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	15.620.301	1.324.373	308.094	31.353	22.099	1.426	466	229	280
16	15.834.383	1.150.558	279.536	26.045	17.436	903	23	2	0
18	15.876.009	1.114.339	269.063	28.537	19.662	1.197	65	13	0
20	14.484.960	2.245.056	531.154	29.846	16.893	879	72	5	0

ESX OPEN5GCORE TRIAL NETWORK

Downlink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	6.670.190	137.584.868	14.429.790	911.493	1.136.623	25.682	1.069	430	414
16	4.028.736	137.930.081	16.713.525	893.830	1.157.008	28.115	149	0	0
18	2.991.048	133.257.458	28.140.177	1.014.748	1.286.759	36.185	1.351	365	8.170
20	1.811.849	117.962.916	44.341.290	1.109.305	1.500.642	42.801	358	0	0

Uplink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	2.345.735	12.318.278	1.365.633	29.064	12.799	1.741	137	31	5
16	1.230.886	13.656.777	1.144.787	27.727	12.168	1.596	83	3	0

18	1.498.528	13.614.004	1.503.464	31.878	17.068	2.562	403	130	31
20	2.248.835	13.262.274	1.106.777	29.794	17.785	2.498	131	1	0

Downlink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	157.214.061	1.243.605	1.997.751	139.198	159.630	6.174	70	42	28
16	156.757.347	1.696.277	1.965.099	146.620	178.457	7.596	48	0	0
18	162.297.469	1.892.764	2.165.425	165.666	205.298	8.275	115	247	2
20	162.256.071	1.664.827	2.397.857	188.140	250.761	11.414	91	0	0

Uplink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	15.649.400	321.287	63.363	21.401	16.683	1.190	70	20	9
16	15.633.779	340.905	62.905	18.142	17.128	1.109	56	3	0
18	16.334.789	218.287	66.037	23.672	23.477	1.500	221	66	19
20	16.121.967	424.211	70.733	24.661	24.693	1.734	95	1	0

ONE OPEN5GCORE TRIAL NETWORK

Downlink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	0	236.500	148.000.219	11.136.826	1.174.352	165.230	19.948	3.416	11.887
16	0	68.011	150.670.668	8.663.685	1.190.629	153.401	25.354	3.940	298
18	0	6.932	142.167.113	7.767.063	2.720.740	255.206	75.504	41.240	131.895
20	0	22.705	151.111.096	6.569.548	2.796.281	221.106	15.881	5.546	21.249

Uplink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	0	620	13.272.942	2.693.851	90.592	13.218	1.819	507	57
16	0	3.696	13.427.727	2.537.654	91.052	10.923	1.725	500	64
18	0	293	13.176.274	1.916.919	202.005	25.711	1.872	326	25
20	0	51	13.991.973	1.862.545	198.904	17.469	1.715	842	107

Downlink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	157.272.124	2.806.224	537.548	96.982	31.090	3.878	494	38	0
16	156.743.996	3.284.515	606.878	98.711	35.598	4.531	572	177	8
18	147.786.675	4.120.609	1.046.309	149.218	56.802	5.698	323	52	7
20	155.049.130	4.306.452	1.217.935	135.287	47.915	5.874	498	225	96

Uplink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	14.961.304	863.259	139.741	62.029	44.490	2.421	336	24	2
16	15.007.089	802.289	149.686	68.325	43.099	2.495	304	53	1
18	14.191.703	736.922	185.736	104.459	100.673	3.632	270	29	1
20	14.956.271	749.948	195.523	100.529	68.411	2.430	322	131	41

ANNEX 4 – MALAGA DETAILED RESULTS

6G-SANDBOX (2024). Data set from the 6G-SANDBOX platforms benchmarking and assessment for different documented trial networks - Malaga facility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373308>

REFERENCE TRIAL NETWORK

Downlink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	36.735.007	82.068.469	45.456.713	1.134.439	100.568	2.612	373	33	277
16	26.246.643	78.116.595	59.288.101	1.729.499	100.064	4.158	844	0	0
18	38.240.645	82.674.540	43.507.801	1.018.002	78.460	1.583	253	2	0
20	28.688.964	79.415.324	55.445.353	1.848.452	92.350	2.023	468	0	0

Uplink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	10.621.255	3.313.054	2.491.379	112.082	7.526	279	101	15	6
16	9.723.814	3.813.910	2.895.384	103.466	8.760	269	34	0	0
18	7.748.463	4.566.553	4.076.247	146.146	7.701	374	143	19	0
20	10.597.674	3.196.729	2.663.514	80.933	6.616	162	43	1	0

Downlink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	126.370.592	32.817.238	6.221.401	72.723	16.316	177	42	0	2
16	109.661.071	50.968.111	4.788.378	49.261	18.747	259	77	0	0
18	101.237.638	59.572.422	4.626.306	70.754	14.047	97	18	4	0
20	100.178.958	58.430.814	6.748.845	114.220	19.915	124	58	0	0

Uplink Delay Deviation Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	13.282.445	2.667.173	549.359	35.008	11.400	199	102	7	4
16	12.529.208	3.352.267	619.984	30.649	13.266	220	43	0	0
18	12.222.009	3.672.156	600.410	39.511	11.237	216	98	9	0
20	11.932.290	3.973.073	594.079	35.716	10.339	127	47	1	0

UPF P4 TRIAL NETWORK

Downlink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	168.162.024	17.440	471	103	69	73	17	0	0
16	168.231.882	19.336	668	236	375	0	0	0	0
18	168.279.219	16.930	1.365	285	702	225	55	0	0
20	168.312.963	17.909	2.156	323	532	151	0	0	0

Uplink User Plane Latency Distribution									
Number of UEs	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	16.775.800	17.543	580	101	9	4	0	0	0
16	16.702.678	90.401	733	183	31	10	5	1	0

18	16.758.772	34.258	855	143	26	11	5	0	0
20	16.660.704	124.374	8.741	218	35	9	9	0	0

Number of UEs	Downlink Delay Deviation Distribution								
	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	168.148.668	30.466	958	100	0	2	3	0	0
16	168.222.486	28.586	1.261	63	101	0	0	0	0
18	168.264.476	31.827	2.238	163	43	22	12	0	0
20	168.300.307	30.983	2.469	167	88	20	0	0	0

Number of UEs	Uplink Delay Deviation Distribution								
	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	16.788.488	4.949	419	163	16	2	0	0	0
16	16.787.995	5.016	651	306	67	2	4	1	0
18	16.787.403	5.892	501	213	53	3	5	0	0
20	16.773.206	19.702	798	300	75	0	9	0	0

POLARIS TRIAL NETWORK

Number of UEs	Downlink User Plane Latency Distribution								
	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	0	62	17.784.287	135.447.442	13.355.916	101.463	7.787	2.254	3.068
16	0	106	18.224.313	134.967.596	13.384.141	142.852	8.643	1.573	63
18	0	70	16.512.662	137.628.173	12.469.638	133.504	8.329	1.416	3.208
20	0	67	20.698.980	134.681.615	11.232.280	116.425	8.877	848	0

Number of UEs	Uplink User Plane Latency Distribution								
	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	0	13.837	4.990.672	10.974.919	676.774	10.776	935	193	3
16	0	7.685	4.219.287	11.727.541	697.718	14.528	1.108	167	1
18	0	15.134	3.916.078	12.052.237	670.613	12.976	922	100	0
20	0	10.667	4.708.160	11.325.024	608.656	14.480	1.096	60	0

Number of UEs	Downlink Delay Deviation Distribution								
	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	68.918.352	56.485.061	38.223.485	2.500.067	567.964	6.943	323	70	14
16	63.609.167	51.736.480	48.224.395	2.610.235	536.612	11.861	464	70	3
18	60.601.676	54.796.301	48.255.885	2.538.527	551.498	12.432	585	55	41
20	56.993.064	55.955.627	50.586.763	2.578.526	612.408	11.943	715	46	0

Number of UEs	Uplink Delay Deviation Distribution								
	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	7.456.562	4.905.884	3.244.011	637.890	418.645	4.643	446	28	0
16	6.861.507	4.994.914	3.730.781	657.793	415.965	6.479	536	60	0
18	6.992.069	4.957.787	3.676.519	634.642	400.536	6.034	454	19	0
20	7.195.229	5.009.313	3.444.348	580.852	430.872	6.884	643	2	0

ANNEX 5 – OULU DETAILED RESULTS

6G-SANDBOX (2024). Data set from the 6G-SANDBOX platforms benchmarking and assessment for different documented trial networks - Oulu facility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373457>

REFERENCE TRIAL NETWORK

Number of UEs	Downlink User Plane Latency Distribution								
	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	96.038.744	67.318.383	1.836.469	122.680	101.269	14.047	51.091	512	0
16	77.209.868	86.116.888	1.726.075	123.059	158.561	27.417	98.730	960	0
18	35.439.338	122.214.536	7.278.566	232.829	247.533	38.359	48.549	944	82
20	73.155.040	89.459.472	2.450.955	146.954	149.142	27.224	79.877	18.692	4.374

Number of UEs	Uplink User Plane Latency Distribution								
	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	3.885.085	12.536.650	68.403	30.224	22.715	2.066	431	77	2
16	5.041.534	11.392.178	59.959	26.380	22.960	1.662	404	141	447
18	7.436.800	8.988.939	62.450	30.950	23.826	2.132	428	82	73
20	2.742.011	13.672.305	77.258	28.189	22.673	1.735	317	24	105

Number of UEs	Downlink Delay Deviation Distribution								
	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	162.520.725	2.899.837	50.166	4.959	7.110	272	84	42	0
16	163.092.889	2.293.089	63.346	5.817	8.769	463	153	32	0
18	161.829.053	3.474.965	147.854	26.433	21.809	537	59	9	18
20	162.425.191	2.888.694	145.658	20.708	10.361	799	279	40	0

Number of UEs	Uplink Delay Deviation Distribution								
	0-125us	125-250us	250-500us	500-1000us	1-5ms	5-10ms	10-15ms	15-20ms	20ms+
14	16.361.729	62.561	49.712	34.561	35.798	1.000	224	68	0
16	16.364.555	61.586	49.076	30.890	38.394	880	179	38	67
18	16.347.044	60.756	59.417	36.575	40.306	1.239	280	38	25
20	16.353.271	61.095	60.577	32.951	36.343	1.111	263	1	14